

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

PROJECT	
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DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN	
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List of abbreviations

DMP: Data Management Plan.

WP: Work Package.

OA: Open Access.

TBD: To be determined.

N/A: Not applicable.

PG: Phosphogypsum.

CD&E: Communication, dissemination and exploitation.

GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation.

LCI: Life Cycle Inventory.

LCA: Life Cycle Assessment.

LCC: Life Cycle Cost.

MDO: Multidisciplinary Design Optimisation.

NGO: Non-Governmental Organization.

1. Executive Summary

In this report, on behalf of the activities related to WP7, a first iteration of the Data Management Plan, containing the key aspects for its implementation and the fundamentals for the following iterations (DMP II and DMP III), is developed. The consortium identifies here relevant datasets in the framework of **FIC-Fighters** project and details about their collection, storage and use. In addition, in the present document, the methods and standards to be followed are described, as well as the guidelines for data management. Finally, the report contains a brief specification of the platforms to be used and their role during the project's implementation period.

The report is directly connected to the activities in Table 1.

Table 1. Relation with other deliverables and tasks.

Task	Deliverable(s)	Description
Technical Activities	WP1 (D1.1 to D1.7) WP2 (D2.1 to D2.4 and D2.5 to D2.11) WP3 (D3.1 to D3.5) WP4 (D4.1 to D4.4 and D4.6) WP5 (D5.1 to 5.5 and D5.9) WP7 (D7.1 to D7.4)	Scientific, technical, economic, environmental and social data.
CD&E Activities	WP1 (D1.8) WP2 (D2.5 and D2.12) WP4 (D4.5) WP5 (D5.6 to D5.8 and D5.10) WP6 (D6.1 to D6.11)	Communication, dissemination and exploitation activities.

2. Introduction

The present deliverable outlines the Data Management Plan for the **FIC-Fighters** project, a crucial element for its proper execution and mandated by the European Commission for projects within the Horizon Europe framework. Deliverable 7.2 in the Grant Agreement is located in WP7 (Project Management) and is closely associated to Task 7.1 (Overall coordination), specifically to the 4th point of its description: “developing and updated when required the Data Management Plan and maintain the Data Repository of the project”. All the partners have contributed to the elaboration of the document, providing the necessary information and describing the datasets to be managed during the project (M1-M48).

During the progress of **FIC-Fighters**, a significant amount of data will be generated because of the developed research in the project actions. All this data needs to be gathered in accordance with specific guidelines to organize, in an effective manner, all the information and make it searchable, easily accessible, compatible, and able to be reutilised (**FAIR principles**). To accomplish this objective, the leading partner (**IDE**) have developed a questionnaire with examples to gather data about the datasets, using the proposed template by the European Commission. The questionnaire is included in Annex of this document. Moreover, IDE has conducted internal online meetings to clarify any aspect of the procedure, in order to collect the maximum amount of information in this initial phase.

After every iteration with the consortium, IDE will identify the gaps after analysing the data management methodology implemented by every beneficiary and propose mitigation actions to coordinate harmonized data processing.

This document, therefore, provides the essential principles and starting point for constructing a comprehensive final DMP. It will be constantly revised during the project in month 36 (DMP II, D7.3) and month 48 (DMP III, D7.4), when a fully data management alignment throughout the consortium will be verified.

3. Good Practices for Data Management

The framework for project development must consider the factors described in the EU's data management guide. Establishing appropriate data management guidelines is essential, as well as comprehending the data that each organization will produce throughout the project. This highlights the significance of the information collected in the subsequent areas. **This document will outline criteria for all project participants, including adhering to a data identification standard, choosing a version control system, and specifying a location or platform for accessing data.**

A primary goal of data management is to provide Open Access (OA) to the data. Uploading documents to repositories and ensuring free access to them are crucial components of open access. To meet the recommended standards, it is crucial to refer to the guidelines and recommendations established by the European Union when creating data or transmitting files. In this sense, IDE has created a Zenodo profile for the project <https://zenodo.org/communities/fic-fighters-project/> (Fig 1), where public information and OA data generated during the first phase of the project have been uploaded.

Fig 1. ZENODO profile for the FIC-Fighters project, showcasing several relevant OA publications

In **FIC-Fighters**, a significant amount of data will be produced from the experimental activities carried out (laboratory tests, surveys, modelling, and simulations...). These will be transformed into more accessible and practical formats such as tables, graphs or documents. IDE will ensure that the produced information conforms to the FAIR principles. The **FIC-Fighters** project will tackle the fundamental information categories detailed in Table 2 at this stage.

Table 2. Type of data potentially appearing in **FIC-Fighters**.

Observational	Collected datasets related to the technical requirements of end products (WP1). Social perception of PG stacks (WP5).
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Experimental	Related to the sampling, characterisation and intermediate scale validation of chemical routes (WP1). Preliminary and detailed engineering of NaOH and AMONI routes (WP2). Experimental results of pilot plants and products validation (WP3 and WP4).
Simulation	MDO of NaOH and AMONI routes and Digital Twins of chemical routes (WP2).
Derived	Summary about chemical routes validation and PG characterisation (WP1). Public summary about chemical routes validation & PG characterisation (WP1), pilot plants designs (WP2), and validation of final products (WP3 and WP4). Data obtained from experimental datasets may be used as inputs for modelling activities, environmental and techno-economic assessments (WP2), calculation and interpretation of data, graphics, analytics of data, results analysis, etc. Exploitation of Results and Business Models, PG exploitation portal (WP6).
Reference/Canonical	A collection of published and/or curated (peer-reviewed) datasets. These kinds of data will be utilised as input for modelling tasks and sustainability assessments (WP2), along with experimental data. It will serve as reference as well for PG Stakeholder mapping (WP5).

4. Data Summary

The data included in the following tables will pave the way for the scientific and communication actions (publishing, papers, conferences, posters, presentations, flyers, and website material). The target stakeholders (academics/students, scientists, society, industry, and policymakers) will have access to the publicly available information and data. The main objective of this preliminary identification is to enhance the reliability in the project results and expand the scientific knowledge in Europe. Achieving this objective will require being open and transparent about standards. The tables will be revised during the project's implementation period on the scheduled dates mentioned in the Introduction of this document, as outlined in the Grant Agreement. As of this first iteration (M6), certain dataset descriptions remain preliminary or incomplete. This will be addressed prior to the second DMP iteration, ensuring that missing details are populated and any newly generated datasets are incorporated.

Table 3: IDE Data Summary

IDE Dataset 1	
Identifier	Modelling and optimisation of FIC-FIGHTERS processes
Dataset description	This dataset comprises simulation data, model parameters, and optimization results of the processes involved in the FC-FIGHTERS project (NaOH and AMONI routes).
Purpose of the data	To provide accurate information on system behavior under various experimental conditions, to obtain optimization parameters for the different processes and to serve as the foundation for constructing a digital twin of the FIC-FIGHTERS processes.
Type of data	Numerical data, model parameters, code scripts, and results from simulations
Form of the data	Digital files (e.g., CSV, TXT, Python scripts). The models will be included in a web interface to facilitate data visualization
Format of the data	.csv, .xlsx, .py, .pdf
Origin of the data	Generated through simulations using internally developed models and optimization algorithms, using input data from the literature, but also data provided by experimental partners
Data Utility	Supports process analysis, upscaling, decision-making in process optimization, and is valuable for future research in hydrometallurgy and sustainable metal recovery
Re-use of existing data	Historical experimental datasets
Data set is:	Revisable
Size of data	GB
Open/Closed	Closed. Dataset specifications are no expected to change in future iterations.

Table 4: USE Data Summary

USE Dataset 1	
Identifier	FIC USE D1.1 Requeriments of the end products 1.
Dataset description	The document addresses the end-user requirements for products obtained from recycling phosphate gypsum (PG) with residues from the aluminium extrusion industry or with ammonia: sodium and ammonia sulphates, katoite and PCC. The requirements for P and REE extracted from PG are also mentioned.
Purpose of the data	Report actions that end with the deliverable D1.1.

Type of data	Information about requirements of ends users.
Form of the data	Text files with images.
Format of the data	Docx.
Origin of the data	Information about requirements of ends users.
Data Utility	Only for project partners.
Re-use of existing data	Yes, we have used the data provided by the partners for this deliverable.
Data set is:	Fixed (already published).
Size of data	961 KB
Open/Closed	Closed. Dataset specifications are no expected to change in future iterations.
USE Dataset 2	
Identifier	FIC USE PG CRO.
Dataset description	Chemical analysis of the phosphogypsum from Kutina-Defos (Croatia).
Purpose of the data	To set out in detail the chemical composition of the phosphogypsum coming from Croatia.
Type of data	TBD
Form of the data	TBD
Format of the data	TBD
Origin of the data	Different analyses carried out at the University of Seville. The equipment used is yet to be determined.
Data Utility	Only for project partners.
Re-use of existing data	TBD
Data set is:	Growing.
Size of data	TBD
Open/Closed	Open. Several data specification remain undefined.
USE Dataset 3	
Identifier	FIC USE PG SER.
Dataset description	Chemical analysis of the phosphogypsum from Prahovo (Serbia).
Purpose of the data	To set out in detail the chemical composition of the phosphogypsum coming from Serbia.
Type of data	TBD
Form of the data	TBD
Format of the data	TBD
Origin of the data	Different analyses carried out at the University of Seville. The equipment used is yet to be determined.
Data Utility	Only for project partners.
Re-use of existing data	TBD
Data set is:	Growing.
Size of data	TBD
Open/Closed	Open. Several data specification remain undefined.
USE Dataset 4	
Identifier	FIC USE PG ITA.
Dataset description	Chemical analysis of the phosphogypsum from Italy.
Purpose of the data	To set out in detail the chemical composition of the phosphogypsum coming from Italy.
Type of data	TBD
Form of the data	TBD
Format of the data	TBD
Origin of the data	Different analyses carried out at the University of Seville. The equipment used is yet to be determined.
Data Utility	Only for project partners.
Re-use of existing data	TBD
Data set is:	Growing.
Size of data	TBD
Open/Closed	Open. Several data specification remain undefined.
USE Dataset 5	
Identifier	FIC USE PG POR.
Dataset description	Chemical analysis of the phosphogypsum from Barreiro (Portugal).
Purpose of the data	To set out in detail the chemical composition of the phosphogypsum coming from Portugal.
Type of data	TBD
Form of the data	TBD
Format of the data	TBD
Origin of the data	Different analyses carried out at the University of Seville. The equipment used is yet to be determined.
Data Utility	Only for project partners.

Re-use of existing data	TBD
Data set is:	Growing.
Size of data	TBD
Open/Closed	Open. Several data specification remain undefined.
USE Dataset 6	
Identifier	FIC USE AW 1.
Dataset description	Chemical analysis of the aluminium waste from Strugal.
Purpose of the data	To set out in detail the chemical composition of the aluminium waste from Strugal company.
Type of data	TBD
Form of the data	TBD
Format of the data	TBD
Origin of the data	Different analyses carried out at the University of Seville. The equipment used is yet to be determined.
Data Utility	Only for project partners.
Re-use of existing data	TBD
Data set is:	Growing.
Size of data	TBD
Open/Closed	Open. Several data specification remain undefined.
USE Dataset 7	
Identifier	FIC USE AW 2.
Dataset description	Chemical analysis of the aluminium waste from Galisur.
Purpose of the data	To set out in detail the chemical composition of the aluminum waste from Galisur company.
Type of data	TBD
Form of the data	TBD
Format of the data	TBD
Origin of the data	Different analyses carried out at the University of Seville. The equipment used is yet to be determined.
Data Utility	Only for project partners.
Re-use of existing data	TBD
Data set is:	Growing.
Size of data	TBD
Open/Closed	Open. Several data specification remain undefined.
USE Dataset 8	
Identifier	FIC USE Report 1.
Dataset description	Report of which systems will be used in the mobile pilot plan.
Purpose of the data	To set out details the different systems will be used in the mobile pilot plant (materials, chemicals components, design, etc).
Type of data	TBD
Form of the data	TBD
Format of the data	TBD
Origin of the data	TBD
Data Utility	Only for project partners.
Re-use of existing data	TBD
Data set is:	Growing.
Size of data	TBD
Open/Closed	Open. Several data specification remain undefined.
USE Dataset 9	
Identifier	FIC USE NaOHroute 1.
Dataset description	Detailed information on chemical data needed for mathematical modelling of NaOH chemical route.
Purpose of the data	Provide as much information as possible to facilitate Multidisciplinary Design Optimisation (MDO).
Type of data	Explanation numerical and chemical about the NaOH route.
Form of the data	Text files with images and tables.
Format of the data	.pdf
Origin of the data	The patent from CapturaCO2 S.L and different scientific articles.
Data Utility	Only for the project partners.
Re-use of existing data	No. This document only serves to understand the NaOH chemical route.
Data set is:	Already published and growing.
Size of data	To be determined.
Open/Closed	Open. Several data specification remain undefined.
USE Dataset 10	
Identifier	FIC USE Risk 1

Dataset description	Detailed information on the human health risks of the NaOH chemical route.
Purpose of the data	Provide as much information as possible to facilitate the Task 2.1
Type of data	TBD
Form of the data	TBD
Format of the data	.pdf
Origin of the data	TBD
Data Utility	TBD
Re-use of existing data	TBD
Data set is:	TBD
Size of data	TBD
Open/Closed	Open. Several data specification remain undefined.

Table 5: MO Data Summary

MO Dataset 1	
Identifier	Desing, Construction and start-up of NaOH route.
Dataset description	The data generated or collected during the FIC-Fighters project will include various types such as text documents, design plans, spreadsheets, reports, surveys and images. The following are the possible data that can be obtained: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pilot plant drawings (m, cm, mm...). - Equipment and instrumentation design (3D CAD models). - Real time sensor data (pH, °C, Pa ...). - Plant operation and control programming document.
Purpose of the data	The data obtained allow the pilot plant to be designed, built and start-up, as well as its validation.
Type of data	Pilot plant drawings. Performance report. Work plan including: Definition of the testing protocol, operation programming, control and monitoring, start-up the plant, commissioning tests, technical analysis.
Form of the data	As mentioned above, the data generated during the project will include various types such as text, spreadsheets, reports, surveys and images.
Format of the data	.xlsx, .doc, .txt, .ppt, .pdf, .dwg, .mp4 or .mov.
Origin of the data	Most of the data is source generated. Once the pilot is built, data collection will be carried out using the following equipment: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reactor. - Pumps. - Flowmeter. - pH sensor. - Temperature sensor. - Pressure sensor. - Level sensor. - Etc.
Data Utility	Magtel staff in charge of the pilot start-up and commissioning. Magtel engineers and researchers in charge of the design of the pilot. Other entities of the consortium that participate in the validation of the pilot.
Re-use of existing data	It considered to use the patent called "CO ₂ and SO ₂ capture process", to be able to understand and design the pilot plant corresponding to the NaOH route. On the other hand, data obtained from "T1.4 Validation of NAOH route at TRL6" will be used.
Data set is:	The data will always be reviewable and could be publishable.
Size of data	Today it is not possible to know exactly the size of data, but it could be up to 1GB.
Open/Closed	Closed. Dataset specifications are no expected to change in future iterations.

Table 6: TMM Data Summary

TMM Dataset 1	
Identifier	Analysis of PG.
Dataset description	Different characterization techniques will be employed to characterize PG.
Purpose of the data	Study REE and P concentration in PG.
Type of data	TBD
Form of the data	TBD
Format of the data	TBD
Origin of the data	TBD

Data Utility	TBD
Re-use of existing data	Probably, we will re-use existing data generated ion the task 1.3 related to the characterization of the different case study.
Data set is:	TBD
Size of data	TBD
Open/Closed	Open. Several data specification remain undefined.
TMM Dataset 2	
Identifier	Production of metals and REE from PG waste.
Dataset description	Results of experiments related to thermal valorisation of acid mining waste and leaching tests.
Purpose of the data	Removal of metals and REE from PG waste.
Type of data	TBD
Form of the data	TBD
Format of the data	TBD
Origin of the data	TBD
Data Utility	TBD
Re-use of existing data	TBD
Data set is:	TBD
Size of data	TBD
Open/Closed	Open. Several data specification remain undefined.
TMM Dataset 3	
Identifier	Fine-tune the NAOH-route plant operation.
Dataset description	Results of first tests.
Purpose of the data	Determine optimal conditions of the pilot plant.
Type of data	TBD
Form of the data	TBD
Format of the data	TBD
Origin of the data	TBD
Data Utility	TBD
Re-use of existing data	TBD
Data set is:	TBD
Size of data	TBD
Open/Closed	Open. Several data specification remain undefined.
TMM Dataset 4	
Identifier	Demonstration of the NAOH route.
Dataset description	Results of experiments during the plant operation.
Purpose of the data	Validation of the NAOH route at TRL7.
Type of data	TBD
Form of the data	TBD
Format of the data	TBD
Origin of the data	TBD
Data Utility	TBD
Re-use of existing data	TBD
Data set is:	TBD
Size of data	TBD
Open/Closed	Open. Several data specification remain undefined.
TMM Dataset 5	
Identifier	Analysis of products obtained in the NAOH pilot plant.
Dataset description	Different characterization techniques will be employed.
Purpose of the data	Chemical characterization of the products.
Type of data	TBD
Form of the data	TBD
Format of the data	TBD
Origin of the data	TBD
Data Utility	TBD
Re-use of existing data	TBD
Data set is:	TBD
Size of data	TBD
Open/Closed	Open. Several data specification remain undefined.

Table 7: ABO Data Summary

ABO Dataset 1	
Identifier	Materials analysis.
Dataset description	Chemical and / or mineralogical composition of solid input (reactant) as well as output materials. These can be solids, or liquid as aqueous solutions.

Purpose of the data	To be able to assess process performance based on mass balances.
Type of data	Tables, in most cases; in some cases, graphical, including photos.
Form of the data	Excel, sometimes graphics compiled as Powerpoint, graphics as produced as output by analysis devices, text-files.
Format of the data	.xls, .ppt, .jpg, .doc, .png, .bmp, .txt.
Origin of the data	In-house analysis of materials, in some case done at an external lab (XRF, XRD, SEM-EDS, CHNS/LOI, ICP-SFMS, microscopy).
Data Utility	Outside the project, others working on or developing similar technology as addressed in this project may benefit from it.
Re-use of existing data	Comparison with results from earlier work (2014-2016) is optional. (Some of that was published in 2016.)
Data set is:	Growing, Revisable, Publishable
Size of data	Typically, a few Mb, maybe smaller. Photos may be 10-20 Mb.
Open/Closed	Closed. Dataset specifications are no expected to change in future iterations.

Table 8: CEIM Data Summary

CEIM Dataset 1	
Identifier	Chemical, mineralogical and radiological characterization of PG and validation of NAOH route at TRL6.
Dataset description	Chemical, mineralogical and radiological characterization of PG according to applied methodologies. Data will be in the appropriate units as a function of product concentration.
Purpose of the data	Study and evaluation of materials obtained from phosphogypsum deposits and validation of NAOH route at TRL6. The purpose of data generation is obtaining data that will indicate that materials obtained from phosphogypsum deposits and validation of NAOH route at TRL6 will be able to be used in the cement industry, in the construction industry, etc.
Type of data	The project will generate data from laboratory tests (physical, chemical and radiological properties of PG samples) and data from the social perception of PG stacks provided by answering questionnaires, communication with stakeholders, events, etc.
Form of the data	Origin files, images (figures), maps, tables.
Format of the data	ppt, .xlsx, .doc, .txt.
Origin of the data	pH meter to determine the alkalinity, XRF or ICP-MS to determine the composition of the sample, alpha and gamma spectrometry to determine the radionuclides, pycnometer to determine the bulk density, sieve to determine particle size, equipment for thermogravimetric analysis to determine the moisture content, etc.
Data Utility	The cement industry, the construction industry, the ministry of environment and physical planning, scientific community, R&D engineers, municipalities, etc.
Re-use of existing data	We will take into account the existing preliminary data, but mainly we will generate new ones according to the work tasks of the project plan.
Data set is:	Growing, publishable.
Size of data	Several GB.
Open/Closed	Closed. Dataset specifications are no expected to change in future iterations.

Table 9: UNS Data Summary

UNS Dataset 1	
Identifier	Radiological characterisation of phosphogypsum. Reports of interviews.
Dataset description	Activity concentrations (Bq/kg). Audio recorded and written interviews.
Purpose of the data	Study and evaluation of materials obtained from phosphogypsum deposits. Assessment of public awareness.
Type of data	Physical and chemical characterisation of phosphogypsum. Reports from interviews.
Form of the data	Origin files, images, audio records.
Format of the data	.doc, .jpg, .m4a.
Origin of the data	Gamma spectrometry, mobile phone.
Data Utility	Scientific community and other stakeholders
Re-use of existing data	Re-use published data of activity concentrations for inter-comparison of the results.
Data set is:	Publishable.
Size of data	Max 1 GB.
Open/Closed	Closed. Dataset specifications are no expected to change in future iterations.

Table 10: CNR Data Summary

CNR Dataset 1	
Identifier	TBD
Dataset description	TBD
Purpose of the data	TBD
Type of data	TBD
Form of the data	TBD
Format of the data	TBD
Origin of the data	TBD
Data Utility	TBD
Re-use of existing data	TBD
Data set is:	TBD
Size of data	TBD
Open/Closed	Open. Data not available in the 1st DMP iteration. CNR will contribute with a data summary for the 2nd DMP iteration, when more information will be available.

Table 11: SCK Data Summary

SCK Dataset 1	
Identifier	WP1: Radiological characterization of phosphogypsum for six different sites using laboratory analysis in SCK CEN and drone measurements on-site (only for 1 or 2 sites). WP3: Radiological characterisation of end products coming from the pilot plants.
Dataset description	Radionuclide content (activity levels) measured by CsI detectors (drones), LSC, alpha and gamma spectrometry in phosphogypsum samples, end products or sites.
Purpose of the data	To analyse and characterize the radiological properties of phosphogypsum across different sites and end products after the recycling process in the pilot plants.
Type of data	Measurement data on radiological activity; includes radioisotopes concentration presented in Tables (lab measurements) and contour graphs with GPS coordinates (drones).
Form of the data	Original data files, images (figures), and text files with XY data columns.
Format of the data	PowerPoint (.ppt), Excel (.xlsx), Word (.doc), and text (.pdf) files.
Origin of the data	Alpha- particle Spectrometry (with PIPS detectors), Liquid scintillation counting (LSC), Gamma ray spectroscopy (HPe detectors), Alfa & beta global and 226Ra, 222Rn for laboratory characterization (Accredited techniques (ISO 17025), and ISO 14001), alongside drone measurements (CsI detector) for on-site radiation levels.
Data Utility	Primarily for the scientific community, research and development, and other stakeholders (regulatory bodies, site owners or site contacts, civil society) interested in environmental and radiological analysis. Important information for the pilot plants in Sevilla and Turku for radiological protection and operation of the pilot plants.
Re-use of existing data	Where applicable, existing data will also be augmented with new findings to strengthen study outcomes.
Data set is:	Revisable and publishable (in consultation with the site owners/site contacts); further additions and revisions are expected as new measurement data is gathered.
Size of data	Approximately few MB < 100 MB for XY data files with metadata, plus an additional <1 GB for graphical representations of findings.
Open/Closed	Closed. Dataset specifications are no expected to change in future iterations.

Table 12: PRE Data Summary

PRE Dataset 1	
Identifier	PEPE portal – PG European Exploitation Portal.
Dataset description	Comprehensive collection of geospatial data, encompassing various layers such as topographic maps, satellite imagery, and thematic maps (e.g., land use, infrastructure, demographics). This rich dataset serves as a valuable resource for a wide range of applications, including urban planning, environmental monitoring, and disaster management.

Purpose of the data	The purpose of the data is to be used to set up a first geoportal in Europe related to phosphogypsum sites, as per activity T6.6.2. of the FIC-Fighters project.
Type of data	Type of data that will be used involves information of the sites with specific geospatial data and information such as coordinates, maps, or satellite imagery. Possibly, some other data could be involved such as radiological data, nuclear activity data, material properties from phosphogypsum deposits.
Form of the data	The geoportal will use maps, charts, graphs, tables, images, videos and 3D models for visualisation. The specific forms of data presentation will depend on the nature of the data and the needs of the users.
Format of the data	For Numerical data: This could include radiological characterization data, nuclear activity data, and material properties data, typically stored in spreadsheet formats like .csv or .xlsx. For Images: This could include purified product curve graphs, potentially stored as .png or .jpg files. For Geospatial data: This could include coordinates, maps, or satellite imagery, potentially stored in GIS-compatible formats like .shp, .geojson or .tiff. For Textual data: This could include metadata and documentation related to the datasets, potentially stored as .txt or .pdf files.
Origin of the data	Origin of the data is from project partners and other locations owners of the involved sites.
Data Utility	Data is expected to be used on the various level, primarily by the project partners, scientific community but also broader community, citizens, enterprises, public authorities.
Re-use of existing data	Yes, re-usage of the existing data is planned, if available. For example, some of the phosphogypsum sites already have some information available about the level of stacks, have performed various measurements on radioactivity, chemical compounds, have used the stacks etc. Some of this information is even public and what is available will be incorporated in the geoportal's dataset. In addition, through the project's WP1 measurement information about the 6 pilot project's locations will also be available and used.
Data set is:	As mentioned, some of the information that will be encompassed in the portal might be already published. All the data will be publishable, however, there might be some limitations on data sensitivity so although major information about the sites will be made public, other information such as sensitive data (e.g. individuals responsible, measurements, usage etc) will be visible only to a certain extent.
Size of data	Depending on a coverage area, data size can be up to several GB.
Open/Closed	Closed. Dataset specifications are no expected to change in future iterations.

Table 13: CCO2 Data Summary

CCO2 Dataset 1	
Identifier	FIC CCO2 CCO2Patent.
Dataset description	Patent of the NaOH route of CapturaCO2 S.L.
Purpose of the data	To facilitate the understanding of the NaOH chemical route for the project partners. Text of the patent published in the SPANISH OFFICE OF PATENTS AND TRADEMARKS.
Type of data	Explanation of the patent used in the NaOH route within the project.
Form of the data	Text files with images.
Format of the data	.pdf
Origin of the data	SPANISH OFFICE OF PATENTS AND TRADEMARKS.
Data Utility	Only for the project partners.
Re-use of existing data	No. This document only serves to understand the NaOH chemical route.
Data set is:	Already published.
Size of data	1.492 KB
Open/Closed	Closed. Dataset specifications are no expected to change in future iterations.
CCO2 Dataset 2	
Identifier	FIC CCO2 NaOHroute 1.
Dataset description	Detailed information on chemical data needed for mathematical modelling of NaOH chemical route.
Purpose of the data	Provide as much information as possible to facilitate Multidisciplinary Design Optimisation (MDO).
Type of data	Explanation numerical and chemical about the NaOH route.
Form of the data	Text files with images and tables.
Format of the data	.pdf
Origin of the data	The patent from CapturaCO2 S.L and different scientific articles.

Data Utility	Only for the project partners.
Re-use of existing data	No. This document only serves to understand the NaOH chemical route.
Data set is:	Already published and growing.
Size of data	TBD
Open/Closed	Open. Several data specification remain undefined.
CCO2 Dataset 3	
Identifier	FIC CCO2 Risk 1.
Dataset description	Detailed information on the human health risks of the NaOH chemical route.
Purpose of the data	Provide as much information as possible to facilitate the Task 2.1
Type of data	TBD
Form of the data	TBD
Format of the data	.pdf.
Origin of the data	TBD
Data Utility	TBD
Re-use of existing data	TBD
Data set is:	TBD
Size of data	TBD
Open/Closed	Open. Several data specification remain undefined.
CCO2 Dataset 4	
Identifier	FIC CCO2 Demo 1.
Dataset description	NaOH chemical route information for the local citizen.
Purpose of the data	To aid the understanding of the NaOH chemical route for the local citizen.
Type of data	TBD
Form of the data	TBD
Format of the data	TBD
Origin of the data	TBD
Data Utility	TBD
Re-use of existing data	TBD
Data set is:	TBD
Size of data	TBD
CCO2 Dataset 5	
Identifier	FIC CCO2 Report 1.
Dataset description	Results of Task 6.5.
Purpose of the data	Explanation of the objectives achieved within the task 6.5.
Type of data	TBD
Form of the data	TBD
Format of the data	TBD
Origin of the data	TBD
Data Utility	TBD
Re-use of existing data	TBD
Data set is:	TBD
Size of data	TBD
Open/Closed	Open. Several data specification remain undefined.

Table 14: ARDI Data Summary

ARDI Dataset 1	
Identifier	The Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) will mainly register data for LCA modelling. The document is an Excel file detailing the name of the partner, the date, the production site, the nature of the process/product and associated flows and quantities as well as the main contact.
Dataset description	Spreadsheets (LCA and LCC data collection).
Purpose of the data	The data generated by ARDITEC will allow the calculation of the environmental and economic impacts of FIC-Fighters routes for PG valorisation, validating the sustainability of the concept as defined in the objectives.
Type of data	ARDITEC's studies will not be subjected to such metadata generation.
Form of the data	Quantitative and qualitative.
Format of the data	For the modelling of the sustainable evaluation, ARDITEC will generate Excel sheets with flows quantities of materials, consumables, and other resources. ARDITEC will then model with SimaPro software capable of exporting Excel formats. The economic assessment will also be mainly executed using Excel format. For the Health and Safety Study and the circular economy guidelines, Word, and Excel format.

Origin of the data	Most of the data will come directly from partners (direct measurements on site) and will be completed by literature and Ecoinvent data when necessary (confidentiality issues, unavailability of the data, among others).
Data Utility	Data is useful for partners within the project (report and data only accessible for the members of the consortium). In case any scientific paper will be published, data will be useful for any LCA practitioner. Economic assessment is strictly non-disclosable information.
Re-use of existing data	ARDITEC will work with both primary (new data coming directly from partners) and secondary data (coming from existing data found in the literature and integrated from Ecoinvent dataset).
Data set is:	TBD
Size of data	The size of the data generated by ARDITEC will be limited to few MB.
Open/Closed	Open. Several data specification remain undefined.

Table 15: EFG Data Summary

EFG Dataset 1	
Identifier	Stakeholder data.
Dataset description	Personal data and views of people, including contact details.
Purpose of the data	Stakeholder mapping to enhance outreach/metrics.
Type of data	Text / primary data / Loose format.
Form of the data	Excel / text.
Format of the data	.xls / .doc
Origin of the data	Surveys.
Data Utility	EFG and partners, respecting GDPR.
Re-use of existing data	In an anonymised way
Data set is:	Growing, adding data
Size of data	2 MB
Open/Closed	Closed. Dataset specifications are no expected to change in future iterations.

Table 16: UHU Data Summary

UHU Dataset 1	
Identifier	Semi-structured interviews.
Dataset description	Text data from questions of interviews to project partners.
Purpose of the data	To know the information about gender aspects required to elaborate gender mainstreaming report.
Type of data	Explanation text, linked to gender performance of each partner.
Form of the data	Text.
Format of the data	.doc
Origin of the data	Interviews to partners.
Data Utility	To know gender performance of every partner.
Re-use of existing data	TBD
Data set is:	TBD
Size of data	1mb.
Open/Closed	Open. Several data specification remain undefined.

Table 17: ATC Data Summary

ATC Dataset 1	
Identifier	2.1. Interview-log.
Dataset description	Inventory of interviewees per case study / general regarding Deliverable 5.1 sources of information (primary).
Purpose of the data	Identify and categorise relevant stakeholders regarding the public perception of PG stacks in case studies and at EU level.
Type of data	Excel spreadsheet / audio or video (each interview will be recorded).
Form of the data	XY columns text.
Format of the data	xlsx, mp3/mp4.
Origin of the data	Own elaboration.
Data Utility	Research use (5.1 report), repository of external communication of the project, inventory of relevant stakeholders (useful for next tasks 5.2, 5.3 and 5.4).
Re-use of existing data	No.
Data set is:	Growing.
Size of data	≤200 Kb / ≤50 Mb.
Open/Closed	Closed. Dataset specifications are no expected to change in future iterations.
ATC Dataset 2	
Identifier	2.2. Public-material-summary.

Dataset description	Inventory of public material collected per case study / general regarding Deliverable 5.1 sources of information (primary).
Purpose of the data	Identify relevant documents or pieces of information regarding the public perception of PG stacks in case studies and at EU level.
Type of data	Excel spreadsheet.
Form of the data	XY columns text.
Format of the data	.xlsx.
Origin of the data	Own elaboration.
Data Utility	Research use (5.1 report) / Organised repository of valuable published material about public perception of PG stacks.
Re-use of existing data	No similar inventory has been found; existing data refers to published material collected.
Data set is:	Growing.
Size of data	≤200 Kb.
Open/Closed	Closed. Dataset specifications are no expected to change in future iterations.
ATC Dataset 3	
Identifier	2.3. Social-media-log.
Dataset description	Inventory of social media posts from relevant informants as primary source of information for Deliverable 5.1 (case studies).
Purpose of the data	Identify relevant social media accounts/profiles informing about public perception of PG stacks mainly at FIC-Fighters case studies.
Type of data	Excel spreadsheet.
Form of the data	XY columns text.
Format of the data	.xlsx.
Origin of the data	Own elaboration.
Data Utility	Research use (5.1 report) / Organised repository of local stakeholders and their discourses about public perception of PG stacks at case studies.
Re-use of existing data	No similar inventory has been found; existing data refers to social posts.
Data set is:	Growing.
Size of data	≤200 Kb.
Open/Closed	Closed. Dataset specifications are no expected to change in future iterations.
ATC Dataset 4	
Identifier	3.1. News-clippings-summary.
Dataset description	Inventory of news posts from relevant digital newspapers as secondary source of information for Deliverable 5.1 (case studies).
Purpose of the data	Identify relevant media articles informing about public perception of PG stacks mainly at FIC-Fighters case studies.
Type of data	Excel spreadsheet.
Form of the data	XY columns text.
Format of the data	.xlsx.
Origin of the data	Own elaboration.
Data Utility	Research use (5.1 report) / Organised repository of news about FIC-Fighters case studies / Stakeholders identification.
Re-use of existing data	No similar inventory has been found; existing data refers to media articles
Data set is:	Growing.
Size of data	≤200 Kb.
Open/Closed	Closed. Dataset specifications are no expected to change in future iterations.
ATC Dataset 5	
Identifier	3.2. Savedrecs-PG-stacks.
Dataset description	Inventory of academic articles as secondary source of information for Deliverable 5.1 (European level).
Purpose of the data	Identify relevant academic pieces of information about public perception of PG stacks.
Type of data	Excel spreadsheet.
Form of the data	XY columns text.
Format of the data	.xlsx.
Origin of the data	Own elaboration.
Data Utility	Research use (5.1 report, also tasks 5.3, 5.4, 5.5).
Re-use of existing data	No similar inventory has been found; existing data refers to academic articles.
Data set is:	Growing.
Size of data	≤200 Kb.
Open/Closed	Closed. Dataset specifications are no expected to change in future iterations.
ATC Dataset 6	
Identifier	3.3. Gov-NGO-summary.

Dataset description	Inventory of reports or documents from Administrations and NGOs as secondary source of information for Deliverable 5.1.
Purpose of the data	Identify relevant reports or documents informing about public perception of PG stacks mainly at FIC-Fighters case studies.
Type of data	Excel spreadsheet.
Form of the data	XY columns text.
Format of the data	.xlsx.
Origin of the data	Own elaboration.
Data Utility	Research use (5.1 report, also for tasks 5.2, 5.3, 5.4, 5.5 and 5.7) / Organised repository of reports about FIC-Fighters case studies / Stakeholders identification.
Re-use of existing data	No similar inventory has been found; existing data refers to the compiled reports.
Data set is:	Growing.
Size of data	≤200 Kb.
Open/Closed	Closed. Dataset specifications are no expected to change in future iterations.
ATC Dataset 7	
Identifier	4.1. Stakeholders-database.
Dataset description	Inventory of stakeholders of the project and characterisation.
Purpose of the data	Identify and categorise relevant stakeholders of the project in case studies and at EU level.
Type of data	Excel spreadsheet.
Form of the data	XY columns text.
Format of the data	.xlsx.
Origin of the data	Own elaboration.
Data Utility	Research use (5.1, 5.2, 5.3, 5.4), inventory of relevant stakeholders of the whole project (WP6 Communication).
Re-use of existing data	No.
Data set is:	Growing.
Size of data	≤200 Kb.
Open/Closed	Closed. Dataset specifications are no expected to change in future iterations.
ATC Dataset 8	
Identifier	5.1. Local-citizen-activities-log.
Dataset description	Inventory of participants in the informative and deliberative local citizen processes per case study, main features and contributions.
Purpose of the data	Identify and categorise participants of the local activities to keep record of their contributions to the project.
Type of data	Excel spreadsheet / videos (each meeting will be recorded).
Form of the data	XY columns text.
Format of the data	xlsx, mp4.
Origin of the data	Own elaboration.
Data Utility	Recording of sessions for research and dissemination purposes / repository of external communication of the project.
Re-use of existing data	No.
Data set is:	Videos will be publishable (after editing).
Size of data	≤200 Kb.
Open/Closed	Closed. Dataset specifications are no expected to change in future iterations.

Table 18: PER Data Summary

PER Dataset 1	
Identifier	Particle size distribution of sodium sulphate.
Dataset description	Measure of the particle size distribution (granulometry) by laser diffraction. Size (μm) as a function of product concentration (%).
Purpose of the data	Characterization of the sodium sulphate obtained from phosphogypsum deposits and comparison to those data for the commercially available samples.
Type of data	Particle size distribution graph (XY) including product concentration, radiation; absorption range, measurement range and other technical data from the equipment and the experiment.
Form of the data	Origin files with graph, tables, Images, XY columns text, presentation.
Format of the data	.pdf, .xlsx, .doc, .txt, .pptx
Origin of the data	Mastersizer 2000 for particle size distribution analysis.
Data Utility	Scientific community, R&D researchers and engineers.
Re-use of existing data	Yes, we will re-use existing data from commercial samples of sodium sulphate for comparison.
Data set is:	Revisable, publishable, re-usable.

Size of data	Single files up to 1GB each, total project data up to 1 TB.
Open/Closed	Closed. Dataset specifications are no expected to change in future iterations.
PER Dataset 2	
Identifier	Test for evaluation disintegration, solubility and residues of solid detergents containing sodium sulphate.
Dataset description	Evaluation of the solubility of solid detergents in water as well as presence/absence of insoluble residues.
Purpose of the data	Perform quality control of solid detergents, ensuring that the final products containing sodium sulphate maintain acceptable solubility and absence of residues during the washing process in dishwashers or washing machines.
Type of data	Data related to solubility profile of solid detergents (disintegration and dissolution time), water hardness conditions, % of non-soluble residues.
Form of the data	Tables, graphics, Images (pictures), videos, XY columns text, presentation.
Format of the data	.pdf, .xlsx, .doc, .pptx, .avi.
Origin of the data	Empirical laboratory data.
Data Utility	Scientific community, R&D researchers and engineers.
Re-use of existing data	Yes, we will re-use existing data from products containing commercial samples of sodium sulphate for comparison.
Data set is:	Revisable, publishable, re-usable
Size of data	Single files up to 1GB each, total project data up to 1 TB
Open/Closed	Closed. Dataset specifications are no expected to change in future iterations.
PER Dataset 3	
Identifier	Formulation of solid detergents containing sodium sulphate in laboratory (small scale) and pilot plant scale.
Dataset description	Description of the manufacturing process (concentration of ingredients (%), stirring time (minutes), etc) for obtaining solid detergent by mixture of original key ingredients and evaluation of key parameters.
Purpose of the data	Evaluation of sodium sulphate impact on the formulation process of powder detergents for any application (laundry or dish washing) and also on the physiochemical parameters.
Type of data	Table with the recipe of solid detergents (composition based on the list of ingredients directly added to the mixture, order of addition, stirring conditions, physiochemical parameters, etc.)
Form of the data	Tables, Images (pictures), XY columns text, presentation.
Format of the data	.pdf, .xlsx, .doc, .pptx
Origin of the data	Solids pilot plant. Empirical laboratory data.
Data Utility	Scientific community, R&D researchers and engineers.
Re-use of existing data	Yes, we will re-use existing data from products containing commercial samples of sodium sulphate for comparison.
Data set is:	Revisable, publishable, re-usable.
Size of data	Single files up to 1GB each, total project data up to 1 TB.
Open/Closed	Closed. Dataset specifications are no expected to change in future iterations.
PER Dataset 4	
Identifier	Physical stability studies of solid detergents containing sodium sulphate.
Dataset description	Evaluation of physiochemical parameters and appearance of solid detergents after storage under certain controlled conditions of temperature and humidity during a long period of time.
Purpose of the data	Making the quality control of solid detergents, ensuring that the final products containing sodium sulphate are stable and remain acceptable appearance and good properties, at least up to after 12 weeks of storage under stressed conditions. This test conditions simulate longer period of storage of the products in supermarket shelves.
Type of data	Table with the follow-ups of the samples including physiochemical parameters (pH, instrumental colour measurements, fluidity, compaction properties, description, time of storage and storage conditions), pictures and criteria for passing this quality control tests.
Form of the data	Tables, Images (pictures), XY columns text, presentation.
Format of the data	.pdf, .xlsx, .doc, .pptx.
Origin of the data	Storage in chamber with controlled temperature and humidity. Other instruments for measuring physical parameters: Fluid meter equipped with motion sensors. Spectrophotometer Konika Minolta and other empirical laboratory data.
Data Utility	Scientific community, R&D researchers and engineers.
Re-use of existing data	Yes, we will re-use existing data from products containing commercial samples of sodium sulphate for comparison.
Data set is:	Revisable, publishable, re-usable.

Size of data	Single files up to 1GB each, total project data up to 1 TB.
Open/Closed	Closed. Dataset specifications are no expected to change in future iterations.
PER Dataset 5	
Identifier	Efficacy test of solid detergents containing sodium sulphate.
Dataset description	Evaluation of primary performance (soil removal capability) of solids detergents containing sodium sulphate in real scenarios (washing machine or dishwasher), under standardized conditions, carried out by Persán or by certified external laboratories of references for detergent products development. Instrumentally data collection and evaluation, by image analysis.
Purpose of the data	Ensure that the new circular sodium sulphate developed within the framework of this project has no negative impact on the primary performance of detergent products.
Type of data	Template with graphics and tables containing a panel of stains, data about the removal capacity of the detergents (“Detergency”), test conditions, machine model, product dose per wash, etc.
Form of the data	Tables, Graphics, Images (pictures), XY columns text, presentation.
Format of the data	.pdf, .xlsx, .doc, .pptx, .csv.
Origin of the data	Digieye (instrument for image analysis), washing machines, dishwasher machines (for soil removal testing).
Data Utility	Scientific community, R&D researchers.
Re-use of existing data	Yes, we will re-use existing data from products containing commercial samples of sodium sulphate for comparison.
Data set is:	Revisable, publishable, re-usable.
Size of data	Single files up to 1GB each, total project data up to 1 TB.
Open/Closed	Closed. Dataset specifications are no expected to change in future iterations.

Table 19: CC Data Summary

CC Dataset 1	
Identifier	FIC-Fighters #WP_name of the data set.
Dataset description	Experimental data in lab notes, reports, presentations.
Purpose of the data	To document and analyse the results of experiments conducted in the laboratory.
Type of data	Numerical data and textual records, such as experimental measurements, notes, and results
Form of the data	Electronic documents in the form of spreadsheets, text documents, presentations, and graphical data.
Format of the data	.doc, .xlsx, .ppt, .pdf.
Origin of the data	Generated from experimental activities conducted by researchers in the lab.
Data Utility	Useful for analysing experimental outcomes, making presentations, and drafting reports.
Re-use of existing data	No, this dataset contains newly collected experimental data.
Data set is:	Revisable and publishable for ongoing and future research activities.
Size of data	Approximately 5 MB, containing data spreadsheets, text, and graphical information.
Open/Closed	Closed. Dataset specifications are no expected to change in future iterations.

Table 20: CSIC Data Summary

CSIC Dataset 1	
Identifier	Mineralogical characterization of products.
Dataset description	Intensity (number of counts) as function of 2theta (deg.).
Purpose of the data	Study and evaluation of the mineralogical compounds in the samples.
Type of data	X-ray diffraction patterns.
Form of the data	XY columns, figures.
Format of the data	.raw, .eva, xls.
Origin of the data	Bruker AXS D8 X-ray powder diffractometer.
Data Utility	Scientific community.
Re-use of existing data	No.
Data set is:	Publishable.
Size of data	< 1 MB/file
Open/Closed	Closed. Dataset specifications are no expected to change in future iterations.
CSIC Dataset 2	
Identifier	Chemical characterization of products.
Dataset description	Composition of the samples: oxides (%wt.)
Purpose of the data	Study and evaluation of the chemical composition in the samples.
Type of data	Excel file.

Form of the data	XY columns, tables.
Format of the data	xls.
Origin of the data	Philips PW1404 X-ray fluorescence spectrometer fitted with a dual (Sc/Mo) anode X-ray tube.
Data Utility	Scientific community.
Re-use of existing data	No.
Data set is:	Publishable.
Size of data	< 1 MB/file.
Open/Closed	Closed. Dataset specifications are no expected to change in future iterations.
CSIC Dataset 3	
Identifier	Thermal and weight loss characterization of products.
Dataset description	Weight loss (mg) as function of the temperature (°C). Heat flow (mV) as function of the temperature (°C).
Purpose of the data	Study and evaluation of the thermal decomposition of the samples.
Type of data	Thermograms.
Form of the data	XY columns, figure.
Format of the data	.dat, xls.
Origin of the data	TA Instruments SDTQ600 analyser.
Data Utility	Scientific community.
Re-use of existing data	No.
Data set is:	Publishable.
Size of data	< 1 MB/file.
Open/Closed	Closed. Dataset specifications are no expected to change in future iterations.
CSIC Dataset 4	
Identifier	Morphological, chemical and mineralogical characterization of products.
Dataset description	Intensity (number of counts) as function of Energy (keV). Images.
Purpose of the data	Study and evaluation of the morphological, chemical and mineralogical characterization of the samples.
Type of data	Spectra, Images.
Form of the data	XY columns, figure.
Format of the data	.jpg, .xls.
Origin of the data	Hitachi S4800 electron microscope coupled to a Bruker Nano XFlash 5030 silicon drift detector.
Data Utility	Scientific community.
Re-use of existing data	No.
Data set is:	Publishable.
Size of data	< 1 MB/file.
Open/Closed	Closed. Dataset specifications are no expected to change in future iterations.
CSIC Dataset 5	
Identifier	Chemical bonds in the samples.
Dataset description	Transmittance (%) as function of wavenumber (cm ⁻¹). Images.
Purpose of the data	Study and evaluation of the chemical bonds in the samples.
Type of data	Spectra, Images.
Form of the data	XY columns, figure.
Format of the data	.jpg, .xls.
Origin of the data	Thermo Scientific Nicolet 600 Fourier transform infrared spectrometer.
Data Utility	Scientific community.
Re-use of existing data	No.
Data set is:	Publishable.
Size of data	< 1 MB/file.
Open/Closed	Closed. Dataset specifications are no expected to change in future iterations.
CSIC Dataset 6	
Identifier	Particle size of the samples.
Dataset description	Volume density (%) as function of particle size (µm). Cumulative volume (%) as function of particle size (µm).
Purpose of the data	Study and evaluation of the particle size of the samples.
Type of data	Table, Images.
Form of the data	XY columns, figure.
Format of the data	.jpg, .xls.
Origin of the data	Mastersizer 3000.
Data Utility	Scientific community.
Re-use of existing data	No.
Data set is:	Publishable.

Size of data	< 1 MB/file.
Open/Closed	Closed. Dataset specifications are no expected to change in future iterations.
CSIC Dataset 7	
Identifier	Pore structure of the samples.
Dataset description	Volume intrusion (cm ³ /g) as function of pore size (µm). BET N ₂ Surface area (cm ² /g) as function of particle size (µm).
Purpose of the data	Study and evaluation of the pore structure of the samples by N ₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms.
Type of data	Table, Images.
Form of the data	XY columns, figure.
Format of the data	.rpt, .dat, xls.
Origin of the data	Micromeritics ASAP 2010.
Data Utility	Scientific community.
Re-use of existing data	No.
Data set is:	Publishable.
Size of data	< 1 MB/file.
Open/Closed	Closed. Dataset specifications are no expected to change in future iterations.

Table 21: LECTA Data Summary

LECTA Dataset 1	
Identifier	Black liquor recovery boiler combustion.
Dataset description	Combustion characteristics and quality of black and green liquor.
Purpose of the data	Comparison between commercial and new Na ₂ SO ₄ .
Type of data	Temperature, heat power, flue gas emissions and composition of liquor.
Form of the data	Recompilation of data in excel files.
Format of the data	.xlsx.
Origin of the data	Recovery section.
Data Utility	Stakeholders, pulp mills.
Re-use of existing data	No reuse.
Data set is:	New data based on measurements.
Size of data	TBD
Open/Closed	Open. Several data specification remain undefined.

Table 22: FRAUNHOFER Data Summary

FRAUNHOFER Dataset 1	
Identifier	Impurity precipitation of the rare earth stream.
Dataset description	Concentration of impurities (% , mg/L, g/L) as a function of different complex agents, time (min, h), temperature (°C).
Purpose of the data	Study and validation of the recyclability of rare earth streams coming from phosphogypsum in battery application.
Type of data	Impurity concentration graph including complexing agents and other parameters.
Form of the data	Origin files, images (figures).
Format of the data	.ppt, .xlsx, .doc.
Origin of the data	ICP-OES, XRD, REM-EDX.
Data Utility	Scientific community, R&D engineers and other stakeholders.
Re-use of existing data	We considered re-using data but found that it does not meet our research requirements.
Data set is:	Revisable, publishable.
Size of data	100 MB of excel data + metadata files, figures presenting data: ca. 1 GB.
Open/Closed	Closed. Dataset specifications are no expected to change in future iterations.
FRAUNHOFER Dataset 2	
Identifier	Electrode production and characterization data.
Dataset description	Rheological measurement, thickness, porosity, solid-content measurement, etc.
Purpose of the data	Study and evaluation of the characteristics of the electrodes produced for obtaining the research goal.
Type of data	Rheological properties (time series graph viscosity, temperature etc.), Electrode properties (length, width, thickness, porosity, solid content etc.)
Form of the data	Origin files, Images, excel files.
Format of the data	.txt, .csv, .doc, .txt, .png, .tri.
Origin of the data	Rheometer, Triangulation Sensor, Thickness-gauge etc.
Data Utility	Scientific community, R&D engineers, and other stakeholders.
Re-use of existing data	Data can be reusable for further insights and recommended experiment.
Data set is:	Revisable, publishable.

Size of data	500 MB of excel data + metadata files, figures presenting data: ca. 5 GB – this is suitable for small scale electrode production.
Open/Closed	Closed. Dataset specifications are no expected to change in future iterations.
FRAUNHOFER Dataset 3	
Identifier	Electrochemical test data.
Dataset description	Test cells are measured with different measurement plans, e.g. performance, rate capability, cycle life.
Purpose of the data	Evaluating the electrochemical material performance.
Type of data	Multi column files: time, voltage, current.
Form of the data	Text files, Origin files, Excel files.
Format of the data	.txt, .opj, .xlsx.
Origin of the data	Batterie testers / potentiostats.
Data Utility	Scientific community, R&D engineers, and other stakeholders.
Re-use of existing data	Not applicable. Measurements have to be done using the specific materials obtained from other WPs in the project.
Data set is:	Revisable, publishable.
Size of data	200 MB of origin/excel data + small metadata files, figures presenting data: ca. 2 GB.
Open/Closed	Closed. Dataset specifications are no expected to change in future iterations.

Table 23: ALDA Data Summary

ALDA Dataset 1	
Identifier	TBD
Dataset description	TBD
Purpose of the data	TBD
Type of data	TBD
Form of the data	TBD
Format of the data	TBD
Origin of the data	TBD
Data Utility	TBD
Re-use of existing data	TBD
Data set is:	TBD
Size of data	TBD
Open/Closed	Open. Data not available in the 1st DMP iteration. ALDA will contribute with a data summary for the 2nd DMP iteration, when more information will be available.

Table 24: CHR Data Summary

CHR Dataset 1	
Identifier	TBD
Dataset description	TBD
Purpose of the data	TBD
Type of data	TBD
Form of the data	TBD
Format of the data	TBD
Origin of the data	TBD
Data Utility	TBD
Re-use of existing data	TBD
Data set is:	TBD
Size of data	TBD
Open/Closed	Open. Data not available in the 1st DMP iteration. CHR will contribute with a data summary for the 2nd DMP iteration, when more information will be available.

Table 25: CIU Data Summary

CIU Dataset 1	
Identifier	CARBONATION TEST BED FACILITY.
Dataset description	Diagrams as a part of the design of the facility. Flows, temperatures, concentrations... as operational and carbonation parameters.
Purpose of the data	Validation of the carbonation procedure of katoite with CO ₂ -rich industrial gases.

Type of data	Curve graphs (time-kg/s, °C, %, ...), lab results, text files, images, ...
Form of the data	Images, ASCII, pdf files.
Format of the data	.jpeg, .xlsx, .pdf, .doc.
Origin of the data	Devices installed in the carbonation test bed facility, laboratory equipment.
Data Utility	Scientific community, R&D engineers.
Re-use of existing data	No.
Data set is:	Growing, publishable.
Size of data	<1GB.
Open/Closed	Closed. Dataset specifications are no expected to change in future iterations.

Table 26: MBAR Data Summary

MBAR Dataset 1	
Identifier	Audio recording.
Dataset description	Audio file from the social perception interviews.
Purpose of the data	Understand the social perception of PG piles. Related with Task 5.1 Interviews.
Type of data	Audio files.
Form of the data	Audio Files in m4a format.
Format of the data	.m4a.
Origin of the data	Generated.
Data Utility	Task 5.1
Re-use of existing data	TBD
Data set is:	Growing
Size of data	TBD
Open/Closed	Open. Several data specification remain undefined.
MBAR Dataset 2	
Identifier	Geolocation.
Dataset description	Geolocation of the sample places.
Purpose of the data	Location of the sample collection on the PG pile. Related to WP1.
Type of data	Web link.
Form of the data	Google Maps.
Format of the data	Google Maps Link.
Origin of the data	Generated.
Data Utility	WP1.
Re-use of existing data	TBD
Data set is:	Growing.
Size of data	TBD
Open/Closed	Open. Several data specification remain undefined.
MBAR Dataset 3	
Identifier	Image.
Dataset description	Images from PG pile and from the sample locations.
Purpose of the data	Related to WP1.
Type of data	Photography in jpg format.
Form of the data	Image Files.
Format of the data	.jpg
Origin of the data	Generated.
Data Utility	WP1.
Re-use of existing data	TBD
Data set is:	Growing.
Size of data	TBD
Open/Closed	Open. Several data specification remain undefined.
MBAR Dataset 4	
Identifier	Report.
Dataset description	Report from the sample collection.
Purpose of the data	TBD
Type of data	Related to WP1.
Form of the data	Pdf files.
Format of the data	.pdf
Origin of the data	Generated.
Data Utility	WP1.
Re-use of existing data	TBD
Data set is:	Growing.
Size of data	TBD
Open/Closed	Open. Several data specification remain undefined.

Table 27: MOK Data Summary

MOK Dataset 1	
Identifier	TBD
Dataset description	TBD
Purpose of the data	TBD
Type of data	TBD
Form of the data	TBD
Format of the data	TBD
Origin of the data	TBD
Data Utility	TBD
Re-use of existing data	TBD
Data set is:	TBD
Size of data	TBD
Open/Closed	Open. Data not available in the 1st DMP iteration. MOK will contribute with a data summary for the 2nd DMP iteration, when more information will be available.

Table 28: GIR Data Summary

GIR Dataset 1	
Identifier	Mineralogical characterization of products by SEM, XRD, FTIR and Raman
Dataset description	XRD powder patterns, FT-IR and Raman spectra, SEM photographs
Purpose of the data	Study and evaluation of the mineralogical compounds in the samples
Type of data	XRD patterns, IR and Raman spectra, SEM photographs
Form of the data	XY columns, graphs, photographs, tables
Format of the data	xlsx tables, doc, eva, jpg photographs, jpg graphs
Origin of the data	Bruker AXS D8 X-ray powder diffractometer, Renishaw Raman spectrometer, Hitachi TM3030 tabletop, THERMO Nicolet Nexus FTIR spectrometer
Data Utility	Scientific community
Re-use of existing data	Yes. Unpublished available data could be re-used
Data set is:	Publishable
Size of data	< 1 MB per file
Open/Closed	Open. Data not available in the 1st DMP iteration. GIR will contribute with a data summary for the 2nd DMP iteration, when more information will be available.

Note: Added after 2nd Amendment

Table 29: MCAR Data Summary

MCAR Dataset 1	
Identifier	TBD.
Dataset description	TBD
Purpose of the data	TBD
Type of data	TBD
Form of the data	TBD
Format of the data	TBD
Origin of the data	TBD
Data Utility	TBD
Re-use of existing data	TBD
Data set is:	TBD
Size of data	TBD
Open/Closed	Open. Data not available in the 1st DMP iteration. MCAR will contribute with a data summary for the 2nd DMP iteration, when more information will be available.

Note: Added after 3rd Amendment

5. FAIR data

The data generated by every **FIC-Fighters** partner will be showcased in the upcoming sections to comply with the FAIR data principles illustrated in Fig 2. In this context, it is possible to address the methods and approaches for achieving data visibility (metadata must be available to humans and machines alike), availability (users need to be informed on how to access the data after locating it), compatibility (data should function with different applications and workflows for analysis, storage, and processing), and reusability (FAIR seeks to improve data reusability via thorough and extensive metadata).

For this initial DMP iteration (M6), the aim is to identify which FAIR principles have been adopted by beneficiaries at this early stage. This work lays the foundation for future updates, during which **IDE will conduct specific monitoring and issue targeted guidance to each partner**. This ensures **consistency in data handling methodologies, in strict accordance with European Commission standards**.

Fig 2. FAIR data principles

5.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

In the tables below, the initial strategy that the partnerships plan to implement based on the data sets identified earlier is defined. **FIC-Fighters** will ensure the datasets are discoverable according to the FAIR principles.

Following this first DMP iteration, specific gaps regarding data **Findability** have been identified. Consequently, **guidelines will be issued** to the consortium to **harmonize data generation workflows** in accordance with FAIR principles. For instance, the **file naming conventions and versioning protocols** established by the coordinator (Table 30) will serve as a **mandatory reference** for the entire consortium. Furthermore, in subsequent DMP iterations, partners will be required to define search keywords and specify whether they will adopt existing **metadata standards** or generate ad-hoc schemas.

Table 30: IDE information about “Making data findable, including provisions for metadata”

Partner IDE	
What naming conventions do you follow?	<p>“Project_Reference_Partner_Document Type_Domain_Title_Version” Example: FICF_IDE_D_7.1_Title_01. a_b_c_d_e_f meaning Document types: A: Agenda of meetings; C: Contractual documents (e.g. Grant Agreement); D: Deliverables; M: Minutes of meetings; P: Presentations; R: Periodic Reports; U: Unofficial technical or social contributions (any other document which cannot be categorized under one of the other possibilities); V: Document Templates; W: Review reports. Domain refers to Work Package and position in it.</p>
Will search keywords be provided that optimise possibilities for re-use?	<p>To optimize reuse, datasets will include a curated list of descriptive keywords in the metadata. These keywords are chosen based on their relevance to the research field, such as MDO (Multidisciplinary design optimization), Digital Twins, engineering designs, to enhance the discoverability of the datasets in search engines and data portals. Depending on the generated data, more keywords will be proposed in the following versions of the DMP.</p>

What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how. (If Applicable)	We will supply rich metadata to enable easy discovery of our dataset, including comprehensive descriptive, structural, and provenance information. We will search and adhere to the most accurate metadata standard regarding the fields of modelling and engineering. If we do not find an adequate standard for the generated data, we will create a custom schema based on cross-disciplinary best practices, carefully documenting our process to ensure the metadata meets the needs of our dataset and its potential users.
Clear versioning approach	Metadata will follow a clear versioning approach, with updates documented and previous versions retained for reference. It will be made available in machine-readable formats like XML and JSON-LD to facilitate harvesting and indexing by data aggregators and academic search engines.

Table 31: USE information about “Making data findable, including provisions for metadata”

Partner USE	
What naming conventions do you follow?	The data set is named based on the type of document for which it is created and then the document version number is added: FIC_USE_Type of information_Document Number
Will search keywords be provided that optimise possibilities for re-use?	TBD
What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how. (If Applicable)	TBD
Clear versioning approach	TBD

Table 32: MO information about “Making data findable, including provisions for metadata”

Partner MO	
What naming conventions do you follow?	The technical deliverables that are prepared during the execution of the project will carry the project acronym, task number, document type and date. FIC_FIGHTERS_TX.X._DataType_Date For example: <i>FIC_FIGHTERS_T3.2_Pilot construction report_Dec2025</i>
Will search keywords be provided that optimise possibilities for re-use?	We will provide a set of carefully selected search keywords to optimise the chances of data re-use. These keywords will be designed to accurately reflect the content and context of the data, thereby improving its discoverability by search engines and databases. Like: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Desing NaOH route - Start-up - Validation - Pilot-plant
What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how. (If Applicable)	In the project, metadata will be adjusted to the existing standards in the relevant discipline. In the absence of specific standards for the project's field, it will be clearly indicated how and which metadata will be used. It is essential to follow the appropriate guidelines to ensure the consistency and quality of data documentation. This facilitates the interpretation, reuse, and verification of the data by other researchers or interested parties. Therefore, special attention will be given to the correct documentation of the data, using established standards or, in their absence, developing a clear and coherent approach to metadata management in the project.
Clear versioning approach	File names will include the creation date in YYYYMMDD format to ensure clear versioning. In addition, deliverable reports will include a data identification sheet and a version log to track changes and updates, ensuring transparency and traceability throughout the project lifecycle.

Table 33: TMM information about “Making data findable, including provisions for metadata”

Partner TMM	
What naming conventions do you follow?	TBD

Will search keywords be provided that optimise possibilities for re-use?	TBD
What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how. (If Applicable)	TBD
Clear versioning approach	TBD

Table 34: ABO information about “Making data findable, including provisions for metadata”

Partner ABO	
What naming conventions do you follow?	Characteristic_Identifier_Date
Will search keywords be provided that optimise possibilities for re-use?	Characteristic_Identifier, For example: Gypsum_X_XRD_Date where X gives source or location or PCCProduct_X_XRD_Date
What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how. (If Applicable)	Data on chemical and/or mineralogical composition of solid as well as liquid (aqueous solutions) input and output materials.
Clear versioning approach	Names of files and documents shall be self-explanatory and in English. Machine-readable formats will be used; original extensions .doc., .xls, etc will be revised if a data storage repository requires that.

Table 35: CEIM information about “Making data findable, including provisions for metadata”

Partner CEIM	
What naming conventions do you follow?	We will follow the unified naming recommendations which will be given by the lead partners.
Will search keywords be provided that optimise possibilities for re-use?	From experience, it is desirable to use keywords chosen based on their relevance to the research field, such as 'chemical', 'mineralogical', 'radiological', 'radiological properties', 'validation', etc. to enhance the discoverability of the datasets in search engines and data portals.
What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how. (If Applicable)	We will follow the recommendations given by the lead partners.
Clear versioning approach	We will follow the recommendations given by the lead partners, and we will use the formats suggested by them.

Table 36: UNS information about “Making data findable, including provisions for metadata”

Partner UNS	
What naming conventions do you follow?	Datasets adhere to a naming convention that includes the project acronym, year of data collection, and data type, such as “Prahovo_FICF_2024.csv”. All datasets are assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to ensure they are uniquely identifiable and citable over the long term.
Will search keywords be provided that optimise possibilities for re-use?	Main keywords is “radiological property of phosphogypsum”, “radiological risk assessment”
What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how. (If Applicable)	We will develop a tailored schema guided by cross-disciplinary best practices, thoroughly documenting each step to ensure that the metadata aligns with the specific requirements of our dataset and addresses the needs of its intended users.
Clear versioning approach	Metadata will follow a clear versioning approach, with updates documented and previous versions retained for reference. It will be made available in machine-readable formats like XML to facilitate harvesting and indexing by data aggregators and academic search engines.

Table 37: CNR information about “Making data findable, including provisions for metadata”

Partner CNR	
What naming conventions do you follow?	TBD
Will search keywords be provided that optimise possibilities for re-use?	TBD
What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how. (If Applicable)	TBD
Clear versioning approach	TBD

Table 38: SCK information about “Making data findable, including provisions for metadata”

Partner SCK	
What naming conventions do you follow?	Data files follow a structured naming convention, including the project acronym, year of data collection, and dataset type, such as 'PG_2024_RADCHAR'. Each dataset will have a unique Identifier for citation and retrieval purposes identifiable and citable over the long term.
Will search keywords be provided that optimise possibilities for re-use?	To aid discoverability, metadata will include curated keywords such as 'phosphogypsum', 'radiological analysis', 'radionuclides', and 'gamma spectrometry'.
What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how. (If Applicable)	Detailed metadata will be provided, covering data description, collection methods, and measurement parameters. We'll adopt metadata standards like the Dublin Core schema for compatibility, supplemented by custom tags where necessary.
Clear versioning approach	All metadata will follow a strict versioning system, with updates tracked and past versions retained. The metadata will be available in XML and JSON-LD formats to facilitate interoperability.

Table 39: PRE information about “Making data findable, including provisions for metadata”

Partner PRE	
What naming conventions do you follow?	Datasets adhere to a naming convention that includes the project acronym, year and month of data collection, and data identifier.
Will search keywords be provided that optimise possibilities for re-use?	To optimize reuse, datasets will include a curated list of descriptive keywords in the metadata. These keywords are chosen based on their relevance to the research field, such as “phosphogypsum”, “radiological properties”, and “chemical properties” to enhance the discoverability of the datasets in search engines and data portals.
What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how. (If Applicable)	Yes, rich metadata will be provided to enhance the discoverability of the dataset through the WMS/WFS feature GetCapabilities that provides metadata about the operations, services and data. Metadata elements: name, title, abstract, keyword list, online resource, contact information. Metadata standards: OGC GetCapabilities.
Clear versioning approach	To maintain data integrity and facilitate discovery, metadata will adhere to a clear versioning scheme. Each version will be documented and archived, and the metadata itself will be available in standardized, machine-readable formats to support broad dissemination and long-term accessibility.

Table 40: CCO2 information about “Making data findable, including provisions for metadata”

Partner CCO2	
What naming conventions do you follow?	The data set is named based on the type of document for which it is created and then the document version number is added: FIC_CCO2_Type of information_Document Number.
Will search keywords be provided that optimise possibilities for re-use?	TBD
What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist	TBD

in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how. (If Applicable)	
Clear versioning approach	TBD

Table 41: ARDI information about “Making data findable, including provisions for metadata”

Partner ARDI	
What naming conventions do you follow?	The Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) will mainly register data for LCA modelling. The document is an Excel file detailing the name of the partner, the date, the production site, the nature of the process/product and associated flows and quantities as well as the main contact.
Will search keywords be provided that optimise possibilities for re-use?	For the general templates: LCA, LCI, Energy, Materials, Waste, Emissions. ARDITEC will include keywords and develop the searching protocol if needed.
What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how. (If Applicable)	ARDITEC's studies will not be subjected to such metadata generation.
Clear versioning approach	ARDITEC internally use manual versioning: Manually creating dated copies of documents and capture data templates to easy access to the most updated one.

Table 42: EFG information about “Making data findable, including provisions for metadata”

Partner EFG	
What naming conventions do you follow?	Loose format.
Will search keywords be provided that optimise possibilities for re-use?	Gender, profession, age, nationality.
What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how. (If Applicable)	Sources of data (surveys, event registrations, newsletter subscriptions), date.
Clear versioning approach	Loose format / text.

Table 43: UHU information about “Making data findable, including provisions for metadata”

Partner UHU	
What naming conventions do you follow?	TBD
Will search keywords be provided that optimise possibilities for re-use?	Yes.
What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how. (If Applicable)	Type of partner, country, date.
Clear versioning approach	TBD

Table 44: ATC information about “Making data findable, including provisions for metadata”

Partner ATC	
What naming conventions do you follow?	None (most of the database are for internal use only).
Will search keywords be provided that optimise possibilities for re-use?	Only for the public videos (tags).
What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how. (If Applicable)	Only for the public videos: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Title. • Short description. • Date. • Location. • Tags (keywords), i.e. <i>#local-democracy; #pg-citizen-forum; #case-study-name-pg-public-deliberation, #ficfighters-citizen-activity, etc.</i> • Representative picture.

	Transcription and translation (into English)
Clear versioning approach	Metadata will follow a clear versioning approach. It will be made available in machine-readable formats like XML and JSONLD to facilitate harvesting and indexing by data aggregators and academic search engines.

Table 45: PER information about “Making data findable, including provisions for metadata”

Partner PER	
What naming conventions do you follow?	Datasets adhere to a naming convention that includes the project acronym, the <u>dataset identifier metadata</u> , the <u>year of data generation</u> , and data type, such as; 'FIC-Fighters_particlesize_2024.pptx'. All datasets are assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to ensure they are uniquely identifiable and citable over the long term (DOI to be determined).
Will search keywords be provided that optimise possibilities for re-use?	To optimize reuse, datasets will include a curated list of descriptive keywords in the metadata. These keywords are chosen based on their relevance to the research field, such as 'granulometry', 'particle size distribution', "absorption".
What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how. (If Applicable)	TBD
Clear versioning approach	Metadata will follow a clear versioning approach, with updates documented and previous versions retained for reference. It will be made available in machine-readable formats like XML and JSONLD to facilitate harvesting and indexing by data aggregators and academic search engines.

Table 46: CC information about “Making data findable, including provisions for metadata”

Partner CC	
What naming conventions do you follow?	Datasets adhere to a naming convention that includes the project acronym (FIC-Fighters), year of data collection, and data type, such as "FIC-Fighters 2024 Radiological Data.xlsx.
Will search keywords be provided that optimise possibilities for re-use?	To optimize reuse, datasets will include a curated list of descriptive keywords in the metadata. These keywords are chosen based on their relevance to the research field.
What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how. (If Applicable)	We will provide rich metadata to enable easy discovery of our dataset, including descriptive, structural, administrative, and provenance metadata. Our metadata will adhere to the Dublin Core standard to ensure compatibility and reusability.
Clear versioning approach	Metadata will follow a clear versioning approach, with updates documented and previous versions retained for reference. Metadata will be made available in machine-readable formats like XML and JSON-LD to facilitate harvesting and indexing by data aggregators and academic search engines.

Table 47: CSIC information about “Making data findable, including provisions for metadata”

Partner CSIC	
What naming conventions do you follow?	FF-CSIC-Technique Acronym-sample name. e.g.: FF-CSIC-XRD-Belite1.
Will search keywords be provided that optimise possibilities for re-use?	TBD
What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how. (If Applicable)	TBD
Clear versioning approach	TBD

Table 48: LECTA information about “Making data findable, including provisions for metadata”

Partner LECTA	
What naming conventions do you follow?	Parameter_Name of the boiler_Type of product_Date.

Will search keywords be provided that optimise possibilities for re-use?	Not evaluated.
What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how. (If Applicable)	N/A.
Clear versioning approach	TBD

Table 49: FRAUNHOFER information about “Making data findable, including provisions for metadata”

Partner FRAUNHOFER	
What naming conventions do you follow?	Year_KWXX_FIC_Impurity_WP4. Year_KWXX_FIC_Electrode_WP4. Year_KWXX_FIC_ElectroCharac_WP4.
Will search keywords be provided that optimise possibilities for re-use?	Yes.
What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how. (If Applicable)	TBD
Clear versioning approach	Yes.

Table 50: ALDA information about “Making data findable, including provisions for metadata”

Partner ALDA	
What naming conventions do you follow?	TBD
Will search keywords be provided that optimise possibilities for re-use?	TBD
What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how. (If Applicable)	TBD
Clear versioning approach	TBD

Table 51: CHR information about “Making data findable, including provisions for metadata”

Partner CHR	
What naming conventions do you follow?	TBD
Will search keywords be provided that optimise possibilities for re-use?	TBD
What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how. (If Applicable)	TBD
Clear versioning approach	TBD

Table 52: CIU information about “Making data findable, including provisions for metadata”

Partner CIU	
What naming conventions do you follow?	Datasets adhere to a naming convention that includes the main letters of the project, such “FF_NumberX_WP1_Date”.
Will search keywords be provided that optimise possibilities for re-use?	Datasets will include a curated list of descriptive keywords in the metadata.
What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how. (If Applicable)	N/A.
Clear versioning approach	TBD

Table 53: MBAR information about “Making data findable, including provisions for metadata”

Partner MBAR	
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What naming conventions do you follow?	Project acronym, identifier, description year of data collection, and data type “FigFighters Image SampleLocation1 2024.jpg”
Will search keywords be provided that optimise possibilities for re-use?	TBD
What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how. (If Applicable)	Absence of a specific standard for our discipline, we will create a custom schema based on cross-disciplinary best practices, carefully documenting our process to ensure the metadata meets the needs of our dataset and its potential users.
Clear versioning approach	TBD

Table 54: MOK information about “Making data findable, including provisions for metadata”

Associated Partner MOK	
What naming conventions do you follow?	TBD
Will search keywords be provided that optimise possibilities for re-use?	TBD
What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how. (If Applicable)	TBD
Clear versioning approach	TBD

Table 55: GIR information about “Making data findable, including provisions for metadata”

Partner GIR	
What naming conventions do you follow?	We will follow the unified naming recommendations which will be given by the lead partners. Internal system of notation (PG sample no + location) is also used
Will search keywords be provided that optimise possibilities for re-use?	To optimize reuse, datasets will include a curated list of descriptive keywords in the metadata (e.g., PG, location, coordinates)
What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how. (If Applicable)	Due to the absence of metadata standards applied to our discipline, we will create our own metadatas, respecting the cross-disciplinary best practices
Clear versioning approach	Metadata will be made available in machine-readable formats like XML

Table 56: MCAR information about “Making data findable, including provisions for metadata”

Associated Partner MCAR	
What naming conventions do you follow?	TBD
Will search keywords be provided that optimise possibilities for re-use?	TBD
What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how. (If Applicable)	TBD
Clear versioning approach	TBD

5.2. Making data accessible

FIC-Fighters will assess the accessibility of the identified datasets in this section (A of the FAIR principles). Several gaps have been identified in this first DMP iteration and have been communicated to the consortium in order to harmonise the accessibility to generated data. For instance, internal and sensitive data generated during the project will be exchanged exclusively via the consortium's secure private repository. Access is restricted to authorized partners, strictly adhering to the confidentiality and non-disclosure clauses defined in the Grant Agreement. This protocol, established by the coordinator (Table 57), is mandatory for all beneficiaries. Conversely, public and Open Access datasets will be deposited in the dedicated FIC-Fighters Zenodo

Community, ensuring long-term preservation for a minimum of 20 years. **These specifications are currently being implemented and will be fully reported in the next DMP iteration.**

Table 57: IDE information about “Making data accessible”

Partner IDE	
Will this dataset generated and/or used in the project be made openly available as the default? If positive, How?	Yes, the dataset generated/used in the project will be made openly available in FIC-Fighters SharePoint. However, due to sensitive information contained within the data, certain parts will be subject to restricted access to comply with privacy laws and ethical standards. To access the restricted data, researchers will need to apply through a formal request process, where requests will be reviewed by our data governance committee to ensure compliance with legal and ethical guidelines. The openly available portion of the dataset will be deposited in the FIC-Fighters SharePoint.
What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	To access and analyse the data from our project, users will need mainly Microsoft Office and Adobe Acrobat, which is compatible with most operating systems. For those without access to Microsoft Office, alternative methods such as LibreOffice may also be suitable, and we will provide references to these tools as well. For proprietary software, we will provide details on licensing and acquisition in our documentation to ensure users can gain the necessary access to engage with our dataset effectively.
If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	For datasets with usage restrictions, we will require researchers to request access, which we will review to ensure compliance. This supports our mission to, for instance, the MDO and Digital Twins development, allowing the use of data to modelling and simulate the chemical processes and contribute to our goals of optimising the PG valorisation through a controlled use.
Timing of re-used data	Open data deposited in Zenodo will be released with a CC BY license or equivalent. If specific software or tools are needed to access or re-use the data, their information will be provided in a text file accompanying the entry in Zenodo. Items deposited will be retained for the repository lifetime of the repository (20 years at least). Additionally, data and metadata can always be traced to a registered user.
Protocols for access	Only for consortium members, that will be granted to access to the SharePoint. In this platform, sensitive information will be uploaded and only the partners will be able to access to it.
Restrictions	The highest level of restriction will be set for sensitive information that will be only available upon request and after internal evaluation. In the mid-level of restriction, all the information that can be shared with the consortium will be available in the SharePoint. Every partner will have access to this platform. Finally, the non-sensitive and publishable information, will be included (when applicable) in open access platforms (e.g., Zenodo).
Identification	Access to the SharePoint granted by the coordinator.
Committee for accessibility	No need for committee for accessibility. Every partner of the consortium will be automatically granted. Open access information will not need restrictions in access.
Data publicly available	Yes, the metadata will be made openly available and licensed under a CC BY public domain dedication, in line with the Grant Agreement. We will ensure all metadata is appropriately tagged with the CC BY license, allowing for maximum reusability. The metadata will include detailed descriptors and access instructions to enable users to locate and use the associated data with ease.
Length of time	Items deposited in Zenodo will be retained for the repository lifetime of the repository (20 years at least). Duration of data in the internal SharePoint must be evaluated and specified.
Only the responsible of the repository: Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?	Yes, Microsoft SharePoint.

Only the responsible of the repository: Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?	Yes. The depository respects the principles of GDPR and is compatible with many document formats (e.g., .doc, .xls, .pdf, etc.), so facilitates coworking.
Only the responsible of the repository: Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?	Data included in the internal repository will be accessible and findable for the Consortium. SharePoint counts on accurate search engines.

Table 58: USE information about “Making data accessible”

Partner USE	
Will this dataset generated and/or used in the project be made openly available as the default? If positive, How?	TBD
What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	To access and analyse the data from our project, users will need .doc processor and .pdf reader. More are still to be determined.
If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	TBD
Timing of re-used data	TBD
Protocols for access	TBD
Restrictions	TBD
Identification	TBD
Committee for accessibility	TBD
Data publicly available	TBD
Length of time	TBD

Table 59: MO information about “Making data accessible”

Partner MO	
Will this dataset generated and/or used in the project be made openly available as the default? If positive, How?	Only data that does not contain personal information or is not covered by confidentiality agreements will be made openly available. Personal data processed within the project will remain closed and inaccessible to third parties to ensure privacy and compliance with data protection regulations. On the other hand, data associated with the programming or control of the pilot being built will be provided to the consortium for validation if necessary, however, it will only be editable in the programming program itself, such as WinCC or similar.
What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	Data will be published in standard file formats such as .txt, .pdf and .csv to ensure that they can be accessed using widely available tools. While specific software relevant to data access will be provided where necessary, it is generally expected that the data can be accessed and analysed using standard open-source tools. As discussed above, for pilot control and monitoring programming data, the specific software and licence used to perform such programming will be required.
If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	Data will be accessible to all consortium partners via SharePoint, except for individual questionnaires, which will be stored securely at each partner’s premises. Researchers outside the consortium and work packages may request access to the data for research purposes during the project once it is approved by all. To do so, a prior questionnaire must be completed to determine what type of accessibility could be granted, in the event that it is decided to provide any type of information.
Timing of re-used data	The data will be maintained in a reusable state for a minimum of 5 years following the conclusion of the project, ensuring long-term availability for future research and reference.
Protocols for access	Throughout the duration of the project, personal data will be stored securely on the local servers of the responsible partners. Publicly available data and associated metadata, documentation and any relevant code will be deposited SharePoint.
Restrictions	All personally identifiable information will remain restricted to

	internal use and will not be shared with third parties. For information that is shared, the use of standard formats, open source software, and thorough documentation will ensure that the data remains usable by third parties, even after the project is completed.
Identification	In order to access project information, people must identify themselves with the SharePoint account that the project coordinator must accept. Magtel will authorize access to those documents that are its property.
Committee for accessibility	Throughout the duration of the project, personal data will be stored securely on the local servers of the responsible partners. Therefore, we consider it necessary to have an evaluation committee for the approval, evaluation, granting of access to personal or sensitive data.
Data publicly available	Due to IPR constraints, some data generated from project will remain confidential and protected against release to the public domain. All available data will be released to the Open-access database that will be created.
Length of time	This section will be populated during the course of the project as more information is gathered about the datasets available for FIC-Fighters . The timing of data availability for re-use will be specified as datasets are finalised.

Table 60: TMM information about “Making data accessible”

Partner TMM	
Will this dataset generated and/or used in the project be made openly available as the default? If positive, How?	TBD
What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	TBD
If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	TBD
Timing of re-used data	TBD
Protocols for access	TBD
Restrictions	TBD
Identification	TBD
Committee for accessibility	TBD
Data publicly available	TBD
Length of time	TBD

Table 61: ABO information about “Making data accessible”

Partner ABO	
Will this dataset generated and/or used in the project be made openly available as the default? If positive, How?	Within limitations described in the Consortium Agreement, data will be made available from a repository.
What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	Standard tools as part of internet browser software should be sufficient.
If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	A password may be put on a document or file, which may be released upon request (and after agreement within the project consortium).
Timing of re-used data	Data will not be made available until pending publication or patent application processes are completed.
Protocols for access	There should be no costs. A password may be put on a document or file, which may be released upon request (and after agreement within the project consortium where needed, as described in the Consortium Agreement).
Restrictions	These are described in the project Consortium Agreement. Also, data will not be made available until pending publication or patent application processes are completed.
Identification	The project consortium may decide to have identifiers that register who has extracted data from the repository.
Committee for accessibility	The project Consortium Agreement describes this.
Data publicly available	Publications will be Open Access under Creative Commons CC-BY.
Length of time	ABO: five (5) years post-publication.

Table 62: CEIM information about “Making data accessible”

Partner CEIM	
Will this dataset generated and/or used in the project be made openly available as the default? If positive, How?	We will follow the recommendations given by the lead partners and we will support the thinking of the majority.
What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	To access the data from the project we will need instructions by the lead partners.
If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	For datasets with usage restrictions, together with lead partners we'll require researchers to request access, which we'll review to ensure compliance.
Timing of re-used data	This request requires an additional definition of the time frames, together with all partners.
Protocols for access	This request requires an additional definition of protocols for access, together with all partners.
Restrictions	This should be further discussed with all partners, experiences should be shared and an optimal solution should be found.
Identification	Personal account on the platform/website used.
Committee for accessibility	TBD
Data publicly available	TBD
Length of time	TBD

Table 63: UNS information about “Making data accessible”

Partner UNS	
Will this dataset generated and/or used in the project be made openly available as the default? If positive, How?	Due to sensitive information contained within the data, certain parts will be subject to restricted access to comply with privacy laws and ethical standards.
What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	To access and analyse the data from our project, users will need Genie™2000 Gamma Analysis Software. GENIE 2000 is proprietary software developed by Mirion Technologies, and users will need to purchase a license to access the full range of its features. Licensing details and purchasing information are available directly from Mirion Technologies or their authorized distributors.
If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	The dataset cannot be bundled with GENIE 2000 software due to licensing restrictions. Users will need to procure their own copy of the software to interact with the datasets.
Timing of re-used data	The data that is collected for the project's purpose will be made available for use in new research or analysis after permission of the WP leaders.
Protocols for access	The data will be available with the approval of the manufacturer.
Restrictions	The data that is collected for the project's purpose will be made available for use in new research or analysis after permission of the UNSPMF team leader /deputy team leader.
Identification	Access levels may vary based on the role or authorization of the user. Specific permissions will be granted by UNSPMF team leader /deputy team leader to control which data the user can view, modify, or download.
Committee for accessibility	For data access approval, evaluation, and publishing, access should be granted by the UNPMF team leader/ deputy leader. This ensures that any use of the data aligns with the project's goals and complies with internal protocols. Approval from these key figures will be required before any data is shared, evaluated, or made public, ensuring proper oversight and control over the dissemination of the project's outputs.
Data publicly available	The data will be made publicly available, ensuring that it can be accessed by the general public for research, analysis, or other purposes with the approval of the UNPMF team leader/deputy leader.
Length of time	The data will be preserved and made accessible for a minimum of 10 years post-publication. To ensure the data remains findable, we will assign persistent identifiers, such as DOIs (Digital Object Identifiers), to the dataset and its associated

	metadata. These identifiers will guarantee that the data can be consistently referenced and located over time.
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Table 64: CNR information about “Making data accessible”

Partner CNR	
Will this dataset generated and/or used in the project be made openly available as the default? If positive, How?	TBD
What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	TBD
If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	TBD
Timing of re-used data	TBD
Protocols for access	TBD
Restrictions	TBD
Identification	TBD
Committee for accessibility	TBD
Data publicly available	TBD
Length of time	TBD

Table 65: SCK information about “Making data accessible”

Partner SCK	
Will this dataset generated and/or used in the project be made openly available as the default? If positive, How?	The data will be deposited in the FIC-Fighters SharePoint repository to ensure open access to project partners. Sensitive data, if any, will be subject to access restrictions; requests will be reviewed by data owners to uphold ethical and legal standards.
What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	Users can access and analyse the data using standard spreadsheet software (e.g., Excel) or data analysis tools compatible with the data formats. Open-source code used for data processing will be shared to support analysis replication.
If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	Restricted access datasets will require a formal request process, with the application reviewed by the data owner to ensure compliance with all applicable guidelines.
Timing of re-used data	Data will be made accessible for reuse following the initial project publication, with an embargo period if required to secure intellectual property. Generally, data will be available within six months post-publication.
Protocols for access	Restricted datasets will require standardized protocols, including user registration and authentication, to control data access.
Restrictions	During the project, only research team members and vetted collaborators will access data. Post-project, data will be publicly accessible after publication.
Identification	Access to restricted data will require user accounts on our repository platform.
Committee for accessibility	The data owner will evaluate all access requests to restricted datasets, ensuring responsible data sharing practices.
Data publicly available	Metadata will be openly available under a CC-BY public domain dedication to maximize reuse
Length of time	The dataset will be accessible for at least 10 years after the project’s end or even longer after publication. Persistent identifiers will guarantee long-term findability.

Table 66: PRE information about “Making data accessible”

Partner PRE	
Will this dataset generated and/or used in the project be made openly available as the default? If positive, How?	Certain data will be restricted to protect sensitive information, in line with privacy laws and ethical standards. Researchers seeking access must submit a formal request, which will be evaluated by our data governance committee to ensure appropriate use. The unrestricted portion of the dataset will be publicly accessible through PEPE GeoPortal and the geospatial data will be available through WMS/WFS services.
What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	Project data will be made accessible via the web portal, requiring no specialized software. Comprehensive documentation and open-source code are provided to support

	data analysis and replication. Licensing information for proprietary software is included.
If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	Datasets with usage restrictions require a formal access request, which will undergo a thorough review by our data governance committee. This process ensures that data use aligns with project aims, ethical guidelines, and any legal requirements.
Timing of re-used data	The data is expected to be made available by the end of project's 28 implementation month.
Protocols for access	The data will be publicly available, no particular log-in for the sake of viewing non- limited data will be released. Authentication requirements will not be in place. However, for sensitive data there will be an access protocol set up with usage terms, licences or agreements so the authorised personnel can access and view sensitive data.
Restrictions	To maintain confidentiality and protect sensitive data, access during the project is restricted to the research team and vetted collaborators, who must apply through a Data Access Committee. Post-project, anonymized data will be deposited in a public repository, streamlining access for researchers. The access restrictions are reviewed annually and may be modified to ensure ongoing compliance with privacy regulations and ethical standards.
Identification	No personal or individual protocol to access the generated data will be set in place.
Committee for accessibility	Yes, it will be set up by the project's General Assembly.
Data publicly available	The metadata will be fully accessible and licensed under CC-BY, aligning with the Grant Agreement's open access requirements. This dedication enables unrestricted reuse and sharing, promoting broad dissemination of the research findings. Detailed descriptions and user-friendly access instructions within the metadata will guide users to the relevant data, enhancing its discoverability and utility.
Length of time	The data will be hosted for a minimum of 5 years after a grant ends. Deposit for the metadata will be in a trusted digital repository that is committed to long-term preservation and provides persistent identifiers (e.g., DOIs) for the metadata records.

Table 67: CCO2 information about "Making data accessible"

Partner CCO2	
Will this dataset generated and/or used in the project be made openly available as the default? If positive, How?	All data generated by Captura CO2 S.L. may only be used by project partners with prior permission and solely for the duration of the project. If any of this data is to be made public, agreements (yet to be determined) must be signed beforehand.
What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	To access and analyse the data from our project, users will need word processor and pdf reader.
If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	For datasets with usage restrictions, researchers will be required to request access, which we will review to ensure compliance. This process supports our mission to advance the development of our NaOH-based chemical route through controlled data usage.
Timing of re-used data	All datasets submitted by Captura CO2 S.L. may be used, upon request, only for the duration of the project. For extended use beyond this period, new agreements must be signed. However, data re-use is yet to be determined and will depend on the project's progress.
Protocols for access	TBD
Restrictions	TBD
Identification	TBD
Committee for accessibility	TBD
Data publicly available	TBD
Length of time	TBD

Table 68: ARDI information about "Making data accessible"

Partner ARDI	
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Will this dataset generated and/or used in the project be made openly available as the default? If positive, How?	Arditec will store data in its SharePoint folders. The service is provided by Microsoft and accessible only to the ARDITEC research team.
What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	Only for CSV files (references about Simapro needed).
If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	Only the partners could access its data on demand.
Timing of re-used data	N/A.
Protocols for access	No public data for confidentiality reasons.
Restrictions	No public data for confidentiality reasons.
Identification	No public data for confidentiality reasons.
Committee for accessibility	No public data for confidentiality reasons.
Data publicly available	No public data for confidentiality reasons. Only for the consortium members, with the approval of the end-users. Most of the datasets (material, waste, energy, emissions, CAPEX, OPEX, among others) are highly sensitive. The corresponding deliverables are confidential.
Length of time	No public data for confidentiality reasons.

Table 69: EFG information about “Making data accessible”

Partner EFG	
Will this dataset generated and/or used in the project be made openly available as the default? If positive, How?	No, due to GDPR constraints.
What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	Excel, word, statistical packages.
If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	Consent forms. Access provided according to consortium agreement. Possibility of anonymised use.
Timing of re-used data	TBD
Protocols for access	N/A.
Restrictions	GDPR.
Identification	Text, loose format.
Committee for accessibility	N/A.
Data publicly available	No, due to GDPR.
Length of time	N/A.

Table 70: UHU information about “Making data accessible”

Partner UHU	
Will this dataset generated and/or used in the project be made openly available as the default? If positive, How?	Yes.
What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	TBD
If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	TBD
Timing of re-used data	TBD
Protocols for access	TBD
Restrictions	TBD
Identification	TBD
Committee for accessibility	TBD
Data publicly available	Yes.
Length of time	TBD

Table 71: ATC information about “Making data accessible”

Partner ATC	
Will this dataset generated and/or used in the project be made openly available as the default? If positive, How?	Most of the dataset are for internal use only, only the edited videos recorded at the citizens' informative processes will be public and available at the Virtual Forum on PG (task 5.5).
What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	None, except for commonly used video-media players.
If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	N/A.
Timing of re-used data	N/A.
Protocols for access	N/A.
Restrictions	N/A.

Identification	N/A.
Committee for accessibility	N/A.
Data publicly available	Yes.
Length of time	TBD

Table 72: PER information about “Making data accessible”

Partner PER	
Will this dataset generated and/or used in the project be made openly available as the default? If positive, How?	TBD
What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	Microsoft software (excel, word, powerpoint or similar).
If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	TBD
Timing of re-used data	TBD
Protocols for access	TBD
Restrictions	TBD
Identification	TBD
Committee for accessibility	TBD
Data publicly available	TBD
Length of time	TBD

Table 73: CC information about “Making data accessible”

Partner CC	
Will this dataset generated and/or used in the project be made openly available as the default? If positive, How?	No.
What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	To access and analyse the data, users will need software tools such as Microsoft Excel for .xlsx files and Adobe Reader for .pdf files.
If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	For datasets with usage restrictions, researchers must submit a request for access.
Timing of re-used data	Data collected for the project will be made available for re-use one year after project completion to allow time for publication and secure intellectual property rights.
Protocols for access	The data will have a standardized access process, requiring users to authenticate their identities through a registration system.
Restrictions	During the project, access is restricted to the research team and vetted collaborators.
Identification	Users will need to have a company account on the repository platform to access the generated data.
Committee for accessibility	A Data Access Committee will evaluate and approve access requests to ensure compliance with data sharing policies and to assess sensitive data.
Data publicly available	Yes, the metadata will be made publicly available and licensed under a CC BY public domain dedication, in line with the Grant Agreement. All metadata will be tagged with the CC BY license to facilitate maximum reusability, including detailed descriptors and access instructions.
Length of time	The data will be hosted and accessible to the public for a minimum of 10 years post-publication. Persistent identifiers like DOIs will be used to ensure the data remains findable, and measures will be taken to preserve it through a trusted digital repository committed to maintaining metadata accessibility indefinitely.

Table 74: CSIC information about “Making data accessible”

Partner CSIC	
Will this dataset generated and/or used in the project be made openly available as the default? If positive, How?	Yes. Asking for permissions of use.
What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	Office and/or image tools.
If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	Asking the partners responsible of the task.

Timing of re-used data	TBD
Protocols for access	Sending by email.
Restrictions	Depending of the use of the data.
Identification	TBD
Committee for accessibility	TBD
Data publicly available	No.
Length of time	According to the GA.

Table 75: LECTA information about “Making data accessible”

Partner LECTA	
Will this dataset generated and/or used in the project be made openly available as the default? If positive, How?	No restrictions.
What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	Excel.
If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	No restrictions.
Timing of re-used data	No reused data.
Protocols for access	No restrictions.
Restrictions	No restrictions.
Identification	TBD
Committee for accessibility	N/A.
Data publicly available	TBD
Length of time	TBD

Table 76: FRAUNHOFER information about “Making data accessible”

Partner FRAUNHOFER	
Will this dataset generated and/or used in the project be made openly available as the default? If positive, How?	Zenodo.
What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	TBD
If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	TBD
Timing of re-used data	TBD
Protocols for access	We suggest that the WP leader submits a template for their dataset and define the accessibility limits and protocol for the partners involved in the WP
Restrictions	We are at the beginning of the project and cannot reasonably answer this question at this stage.
Identification	We aim to use Zenodo for storing data, so we do not have any special modalities other than what is available within the Zenodo archival system.
Committee for accessibility	Consortium partners and lead beneficiaries will have to decide on this.
Data publicly available	In principle, yes.
Length of time	10 years post-publication.

Table 77: ALDA information about “Making data accessible”

Partner	
Will this dataset generated and/or used in the project be made openly available as the default? If positive, How?	TBD
What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	TBD
If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	TBD
Timing of re-used data	TBD
Protocols for access	TBD
Restrictions	TBD
Identification	TBD
Committee for accessibility	TBD
Data publicly available	TBD
Length of time	TBD

Table 78: CHR information about “Making data accessible”

Partner CHR	
Will this dataset generated and/or used in the project be made openly available as the default? If positive, How?	TBD
What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	TBD
If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	TBD
Timing of re-used data	TBD
Protocols for access	TBD
Restrictions	TBD
Identification	TBD
Committee for accessibility	TBD
Data publicly available	TBD
Length of time	TBD

Table 79: CIU information about “Making data accessible”

Partner CIU	
Will this dataset generated and/or used in the project be made openly available as the default? If positive, How?	Yes, the dataset generated/used in the project will be made openly available in the cloud of the project.
What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	Microsoft package, pdf reader or similar.
If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	No restrictions.
Timing of re-used data	No restrictions.
Protocols for access	Formal requesting.
Restrictions	No restrictions.
Identification	No protocol.
Committee for accessibility	No needed.
Data publicly available	We agree with the GA.
Length of time	For a minimum of 10 years post-publication.

Table 80: MBAR information about “Making data accessible”

Partner MBAR	
Will this dataset generated and/or used in the project be made openly available as the default? If positive, How?	TBD
What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	TBD
If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	TBD
Timing of re-used data	TBD
Protocols for access	TBD
Restrictions	TBD
Identification	TBD
Committee for accessibility	TBD
Data publicly available	TBD
Length of time	TBD

Table 81: MOK information about “Making data accessible”

Associated Partner MOK	
Will this dataset generated and/or used in the project be made openly available as the default? If positive, How?	TBD
What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	TBD
If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	TBD
Timing of re-used data	TBD
Protocols for access	TBD
Restrictions	TBD
Identification	TBD
Committee for accessibility	TBD
Data publicly available	TBD

Length of time	TBD
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Table 82: GIR information about “Making data accessible”

Partner GIR	
Will this dataset generated and/or used in the project be made openly available as the default? If positive, How?	Within limitations described in the Consortium Agreement, data will be made available from a repository hosted by our server and partially offered as supplementary materials in a publication (target journal: Geosciences, MDPI).
What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	Microsoft software>(* .doc, * .xls, * .jpg), Bruker software (*.eva, *.raw)
If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	No restrictions to use, excepting copy-right rules
Timing of re-used data	No restrictions.
Protocols for access	By request.
Restrictions	No restrictions.
Identification	No protocol
Committee for accessibility	Not needed.
Data publicly available	Public data, open-source publications.
Length of time	The data will kept accessible to the public for a minimum of 10 years post-publication.

Note: Added after 2nd Amendment

Table 83: MCAR information about “Making data accessible”

Associated Partner MCAR	
Will this dataset generated and/or used in the project be made openly available as the default? If positive, How?	TBD
What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	TBD
If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	TBD
Timing of re-used data	TBD
Protocols for access	TBD
Restrictions	TBD
Identification	TBD
Committee for accessibility	TBD
Data publicly available	TBD
Length of time	TBD

Note: Added after 3rd Amendment

5.3. Making data interoperable

In this part, the consortium will evaluate the interoperability of the data (I of FAIR principles), signifying the creation of systems to develop a standardised approach for the data to guarantee access for all partners. Metadata vocabularies, standards and methodologies are well defined in the Grant Agreement (Table 84) and will be adopted by the entire consortium after this first DMP iteration. All these changes will be reflected in the second document (DMP II) of the FIC-Fighters DMP.

Table 84: IDE information about “Making data interoperable”

Partner IDE	
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?	The preferred data formats will be those that facilitate the interoperability of the data, i.e., non-proprietary; open, documented standards; in common usage by the research community; using standard character encodings (ASCII, UTF-8); and preferably uncompressed. The data deposited in Zenodo will be described with rich metadata compliant with DataCite’s Metadata Schema. Additionally, the FIC-Fighters project will comply with European and international standards to establish a common research data terminology within the specific fields of activity. Examples of the standards to be used are innovation management (CEN/TS 16555-1), environmental management (CEN/SS S26), waste management (CEN/TC 183), units and symbols (CEN/SS F02), energy efficiency and saving calculation (CEN/CLC/JWG

	4), assessment of workplace exposure to chemical and biological agents (CEN/TC 137) and potentially explosive atmospheres (CEN/TC 305).
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Table 85: USE information about “Making data interoperable”

Partner USE	
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?	TBD

Table 86: MO information about “Making data interoperable”

Partner MO	
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?	Standard file formats will be used, as mentioned above. Each dataset will be accompanied by standard metadata to ensure compatibility and interoperability with other datasets and platforms such as .xml, .pdf, .csv.

Table 87: TMM information about “Making data interoperable”

Partner TMM	
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?	TBD

Table 88: ABO information about “Making data interoperable”

Partner ABO	
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?	Vocabularies: conventional chemistry / chemical engineering terminology. Using English, comprehensible for chemical process and mineral / mining industry. FAIR data principles shall be used, conventional commonly used file formats such as .xls, .doc, pdf, .csv, .jpg, .bmp will be used for all documents to facilitate easy access and use.

Table 89: CEIM information about “Making data interoperable”

Partner CEIM	
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?	Data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies recommended by leading partners will be used and followed.

Table 90: UNS information about “Making data interoperable”

Partner UNS	
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?	To ensure our data is interoperable, we will follow widely recognized data and metadata vocabularies, standards, and methodologies from relevant fields. For metadata, we will implement METS (Metadata Encoding and Transmission Standard) to organize and transfer metadata within digital repositories. Regarding data standards, we will adopt the FAIR Principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) to guarantee that the data is structured for ease of sharing and reuse. To maintain uniform terminology related to the radiological properties of materials like phosphogypsum, we will utilize ICRP (International Commission on Radiological Protection) definitions. For methodologies, we will employ Open Data Sharing Protocols, enabling our data to integrate seamlessly with other systems through standard APIs and data exchange tools.

Table 91: CNR information about “Making data interoperable”

Partner CNR	
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?	TBD

Table 92: SCK information about “Making data interoperable”

Partner SCK	
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?	We will follow the Dublin Core standard for metadata and controlled vocabularies to ensure consistency and ease of integration with other data. Data will be in CSV format to

follow to make your data interoperable?	facilitate reuse, while metadata will be in XML and/or JSON for interoperability with various software systems.
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Table 93: PRE information about “Making data interoperable”

Partner PRE	
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?	We will employ widely recognized and open geospatial data formats such as GeoJSON, Shapefile (.shp), and GeoTIFF. These formats are compatible with a broad range of GIS software and tools, promoting seamless data exchange and integration. We will also adopt established metadata standards like the ISO 19115 Geographic Information Metadata Standard and the INSPIRE Metadata Regulation. These standards provide a comprehensive framework for describing geospatial data, facilitating discovery, assessment, and reuse. It is planned to utilize established vocabularies and ontologies relevant to the specific thematic layers of our geospatial data. For example, we might use the Land Cover Classification System (LCCS) for land use data or the INSPIRE Data Specifications for environmental data. Finally, we will implement standard web services, such as the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) Web Feature Service (WFS) and Web Map Service (WMS), to enable dynamic data access and visualization.

Table 94: CCO2 information about “Making data interoperable”

Partner CCO2	
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?	TBD

Table 95: ARDI information about “Making data interoperable”

Partner ARDI	
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?	N/A.

Table 96: EFG information about “Making data interoperable”

Partner EFG	
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?	Loose format.

Table 97: UHU information about “Making data interoperable”

Partner UHU	
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?	TBD

Table 98: ATC information about “Making data interoperable”

Partner ATC	
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?	N/A.

Table 99: PER information about “Making data interoperable”

Partner PER	
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?	TBD

Table 100: CC information about “Making data interoperable”

Partner CC	
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?	<p>The datasets will be structured using widely accepted formats such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CSV for tabular data, which is easy to use, widely supported, and facilitates interoperability across different software platforms. • JSON for structured data, which is lightweight and easy to parse, making it suitable for web applications and APIs. • XML for documents that require a more complex structure, enabling better data interchange among systems.

Table 101: CSIC information about “Making data interoperable”

Partner CSIC	
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?	TBD

Table 102: LECTA information about “Making data interoperable”

Partner LECTA	
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?	Will be explained when all the control parameters are defined.

Table 103: FRAUNHOFER information about “Making data interoperable”

Partner FRAUNHOFER	
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?	Innovation management (CEN/TS 16555-1), environmental management (CEN/SS S26), waste management (CEN/TC 183), units and symbols (CEN/SS F02).

Table 104: ALDA information about “Making data interoperable”

Partner ALDA	
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?	TBD

Table 105: CHR information about “Making data interoperable”

Partner CHR	
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?	TBD

Table 106: CIU information about “Making data interoperable”

Partner CIU	
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?	We will use standards.

Table 107: MBAR information about “Making data interoperable”

Partner MBAR	
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?	TBD

Table 108: MOK information about “Making data interoperable”

Associated Partner MOK	
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?	TBD

Table 109: GIR information about “Making data interoperable”

Partner GIR	
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?	Vocabularies: mineralogy / crystallography / ore processing terminology. Specific standards given by the partner FRAUNHOFER. Use of English and terms comprehensible for all users (e.g., mineralogists, ore processors, chemical engineers, environmentalists). FAIR data principles shall be used, conventional commonly used file formats such as *.xls, *.doc, *.pdf, *.jpg, *.bmp will be used for all documents.

Note: Added after 2nd Amendment

Table 110: MCAR information about “Making data interoperable”

Associated Partner MCAR	
What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?	TBD

Note: Added after 3rd Amendment

5.4. Increase data re-use

Throughout the execution of the project, the factors related to licensing and reusing the data will be evaluated on a case-by-case basis (R of FAIR principles). As it is specified in the Grant Agreement, Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) license will be adopted to license the project data and allow the widest reusability. This is already reflected for the coordinator (Table 111) and will be adopted by the consortium after this first iteration. Data will be available immediately after publication in the Zenodo Repository if no IPR is applicable, where will remain 20 years at least.

Table 111: IDE information about “Increase data re-use”

Partner IDE	
How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	The research team will license the dataset generated under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) license. This license permits others to share, copy, distribute, and transmit the data, as well as to adapt it for any purpose, even commercially, as long as proper attribution is given to the original creators.
When will the data be made available for re-use?	The dataset will be made available for reuse by the research team immediately following the publication of their initial research findings, if no IPR are applicable. Upon release, the data will be deposited in the Zenodo Repository, where it will be publicly accessible.
Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	The data produced by the IDE team will be useable by third parties, especially after the conclusion of the project. The team will ensure usability by employing standard, non-proprietary data formats. Comprehensive metadata in accordance with the Dublin Core schema will be provided, a data dictionary, and a user guide with the data collection and analysis methodologies.
How long is it intended that the data remains reusable?	Data deposited will be retained for the repository lifetime of the Zenodo repository (20 years at least).

Table 112: USE information about “Increase data re-use”

Partner USE	
How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	TBD
When will the data be made available for re-use?	TBD
Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	TBD
How long is it intended that the data remains reusable?	TBD

Table 113: MO information about “Increase data re-use”

Partner MO	
How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	To maximise the potential for re-use, all data produced by the project will be licensed under Creative Commons (CC) licenses, ensuring that the data is freely available while respecting the rights of the original creators.
When will the data be made available for re-use?	As mentioned above, the data will be maintained in a reusable state for a minimum of 5 years following the conclusion of the project, ensuring long-term availability for future research and reference.
Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	All personally identifiable information will remain restricted to internal use and will not be shared with third parties. For information that is shared, the use of standard formats, open-source software, and thorough documentation will ensure that the data remains usable by third parties, even after the project is completed.
How long is it intended that the data remains reusable?	The data will be available for re-use for the duration of the project.

Table 114: TMM information about “Increase data re-use”

Partner TMM	
How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	TBD
When will the data be made available for re-use?	TBD
Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	TBD
How long is it intended that the data remains reusable?	TBD

Table 115: ABO information about “Increase data re-use”

Partner ABO	
How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	Similar to the publications, under the CC BY license.
When will the data be made available for re-use?	If the data cannot be downloaded or otherwise extracted from a repository, it will be provided as e-mail message. (After OK for the project consortium as described in the Consortium Agreement).
Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	For a certain period of time, as described in the Consortium Agreement.
How long is it intended that the data remains reusable?	Intended for ABO: five (5) years after the end of project.

Table 116: CEIM information about “Increase data re-use”

Partner CEIM	
How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	The CEIM team and the leading partners will further decide how they will license the dataset generated from the project.
When will the data be made available for re-use?	According to Annex 1 (part B), the data will be deposited in Zenodo, a repository funded by the EC and managed by CERN that complies with many FAIR principles. The use of Zenodo is free of charge. The data will be deposited in the PEPE PG Exploitation Portal for Europe where it will be publicly accessible.
Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	This issue should be discussed with all partners and joint decisions should be made.
How long is it intended that the data remains reusable?	This issue should be discussed with all partners and joint decisions should be made.

Table 117: UNS information about “Increase data re-use”

Partner UNS	
How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	We plan to use Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) License which allows others to distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon the data, even commercially, as long as they give appropriate credit to the original source. This is one of the most permissive licenses, promoting widespread reuse while ensuring proper attribution.
When will the data be made available for re-use?	The dataset will be made available for reuse by the research team immediately following the publication of their initial research findings.
Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	The data produced by the research team will be useable by third parties, especially after the conclusion of the project. The team will ensure usability by employing standard, non-proprietary data GA number: 101135157 formats such as CSV.
How long is it intended that the data remains reusable?	TBD

Table 118: CNR information about “Increase data re-use”

Partner CNR	
How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	TBD
When will the data be made available for re-use?	TBD
Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	TBD
How long is it intended that the data remains reusable?	TBD

Table 119: SCK information about “Increase data re-use”

Partner SCK	
How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	The dataset will be licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 (CC BY 4.0), permitting sharing, adaptation, and commercial use, provided attribution is given to the original creators.
When will the data be made available for re-use?	Data will be available for reuse immediately following publication.

Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	The dataset will be made usable for third parties post-project through standardized, non-proprietary formats (CSV) and thorough documentation.
How long is it intended that the data remains reusable?	We aim for indefinite reusability, with regular integrity checks and migrations to maintain accessibility.

Table 120: PRE information about “Increase data re-use”

Partner PRE	
How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	To permit the widest reuse possible, the geospatial data on the web portal will be licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) license. This license allows users to freely distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon the data, even commercially, as long as they provide attribution to the original creators. This open licensing approach encourages collaboration, innovation, and the development of new applications and services based on the geospatial data. It also aligns with the principles of open data and open science, promoting transparency, reproducibility, and the advancement of knowledge.
When will the data be made available for re-use?	The research team will release the dataset for public reuse immediately after publishing their initial research findings. The data will be available through PEPE GeoPortal and WMS/WFS services.
Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	Data will be usable by third parties’ post-project. Standard formats (CSV, NetCDF), metadata (Dublin Core), data dictionary, and user guide will be provided to ensure accessibility.
How long is it intended that the data remains reusable?	The data will be hosted for a minimum of 5 years after a grant end but can also be moved to some other, longer lasting Repository.

Table 121: CCO2 information about “Increase data re-use”

Partner CCO2	
How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	TBD
When will the data be made available for re-use?	TBD
Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	TBD
How long is it intended that the data remains reusable?	TBD

Table 122: ARDI information about “Increase data re-use”

Partner ARDI	
How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	N/A.
When will the data be made available for re-use?	No, all data will be confidential as explained above.
Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	No, all data will be confidential as explained above.
How long is it intended that the data remains reusable?	N/A.

Table 123: EFG information about “Increase data re-use”

Partner EFG	
How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	CC, via Zenodo (only applicable to anonymised data).
When will the data be made available for re-use?	As soon as possible (only applicable to anonymised data).
Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	Yes (only applicable to anonymised data).
How long is it intended that the data remains reusable?	Unlimited (only applicable to anonymised data).

Table 124: UHU information about “Increase data re-use”

Partner UHU	
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How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	TBD
When will the data be made available for re-use?	TBD
Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	TBD
How long is it intended that the data remains reusable?	TBD

Table 125: ATC information about “Increase data re-use”

Partner ATC	
How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	TBD
When will the data be made available for re-use?	TBD
Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	TBD
How long is it intended that the data remains reusable?	TBD

Table 126: PER information about “Increase data re-use”

Partner PER	
How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	TBD
When will the data be made available for re-use?	TBD
Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	TBD
How long is it intended that the data remains reusable?	TBD

Table 127: CC information about “Increase data re-use”

Partner CC	
How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	The research team will license the dataset generated from the project under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) license. This license allows others to share, copy, distribute, and adapt the data for any purpose, including commercial use, as long as they provide appropriate credit to the original creators. This framework promotes re-use, sharing, and distribution, thereby enhancing collaboration and innovation in the research community.
When will the data be made available for re-use?	The dataset will be made available for reuse immediately following the publication of the initial research findings.
Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	No in general.
How long is it intended that the data remains reusable?	Indefinitely.

Table 128: CSIC information about “Increase data re-use”

Partner CSIC	
How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	TBD
When will the data be made available for re-use?	TBD
Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	TBD
How long is it intended that the data remains reusable?	TBD

Table 129: LECTA information about “Increase data re-use”

Partner LECTA	
How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	TBD
When will the data be made available for re-use?	TBD
Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	TBD
How long is it intended that the data remains reusable?	TBD

Table 130: FRAUNHOFER information about “Increase data re-use”

Partner FRAUNHOFER	
How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	The processed data and meta data are available under the CC-BY-4.0 Creative Commons license.
When will the data be made available for re-use?	Immediately following publication.
Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	The data produced by the research team will be useable by third parties, especially after the conclusion of the project.

How long is it intended that the data remains reusable?	Indefinitely.
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Table 131: ALDA information about “Increase data re-use”

Partner ALDA	
How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	TBD
When will the data be made available for re-use?	TBD
Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	TBD
How long is it intended that the data remains reusable?	TBD

Table 132: CHR information about “Increase data re-use”

Partner CHR	
How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	TBD
When will the data be made available for re-use?	TBD
Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	TBD
How long is it intended that the data remains reusable?	TBD

Table 133: CIU information about “Increase data re-use”

Partner CIU	
How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	N/A.
When will the data be made available for re-use?	The dataset will be made available for reuse by the research team immediately through the publication of the results.
Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	The data produced by the research team will be useable by third parties with formal requesting.
How long is it intended that the data remains reusable?	N/A.

Table 134: MBAR information about “Increase data re-use”

Partner MBAR	
How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	TBD
When will the data be made available for re-use?	TBD
Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	TBD
How long is it intended that the data remains reusable?	TBD

Table 135: MOK information about “Increase data re-use”

Associated Partner MOK	
How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	TBD
When will the data be made available for re-use?	TBD
Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	TBD
How long is it intended that the data remains reusable?	TBD

Table 136: GIR information about “Increase data re-use”

Partner GIR	
How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	The research team will license the dataset generated from the project under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) license.
When will the data be made available for re-use?	Data could be reused immediately after publication.
Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	All data produced will be useable by third parties, as many of these data will be published in an open-source journal.
How long is it intended that the data remains reusable?	Indefinitely.

Note: Added after 2nd Amendment

Table 137: MCAR information about “Increase data re-use”

Associated Partner MCAR	
How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	TBD
When will the data be made available for re-use?	TBD

Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	TBD
How long is it intended that the data remains reusable?	TBD

Note: Added after 3rd Amendment

6. Other research outputs

As of the current stage of the project (M6), no 'other research outputs' (whether digital or physical) have been generated or re-used by the consortium. Consequently, specific management measures for such items are not applicable at this time. Future DMP iterations will monitor this status and detail the FAIR management of any such outputs should they arise during the project execution.

7. Allocation of resources

The **FIC-Fighters** project depends on a dedicated and secure online storage platform created and managed by the coordinator entity IDE (Teams SharePoint) for the uploading and assessment of all outcomes (including documents, reports, and various files). Additionally, the collaborative space will function as an internal communication tool. IDE will remain in charge of the well-functioning and maintenance of this shared space.

IDE will take the lead as well within the consortium to choose the final Data Management Platform for public initiatives: Zenodo. By utilizing this final approach to assess the data, the partnership will be able to disseminate scientific results pertaining to the **FIC-Fighters** initiative, maintaining the published information a minimum of 20 years.

8. Data security

The digital assets and resources of the project will be safely stored and overseen by skilled IT system administrators and experts from every organization. As noted in the previous tables, certain datasets are saved on internal computers/laptops; therefore, security measures are already woven into their internal workflows. Consequently, each partner will adopt essential security protocols in line with the directives of their respective companies. The responsibility for protecting the data in the **FIC-Fighters** shared repository platforms will depend on IDE.

Moreover, partners of **FIC-Fighters** will maintain data security by following recognized practices.

- Precaution: keep the data in two different locations to prevent losing information.
- Restrict the use of USB and various storage devices.
- Categorization: Methodically arrange data to ensure consistency within the resulting dataset.
- Data sharing must follow ethical and legal standards, encompassing intellectual property rights and data protection protocols.
- Maintenance: Horizon Europe mandates that research data be preserved and accessible for at least 10 years after the project's conclusion.

9. Ethics

An ethical issue must be addressed in the data management of the project. Completing various tasks is anticipated to lead to managing personal information. The personal data will be governed by EU Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR). The administration of the research data will adhere to the same protocols as the management of the consortium's personal data, which will be elaborated upon and incorporated in subsequent versions of this plan.

10. Other issues

N/A

11. Bibliography

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HISTORY OF CHANGES		
VERSION	PUBLICATION DATE	CHANGE
1.0	15.11.2024	First draft
1.1	18.11.2024	Review of the first draft.
1.2	25.11.2024	Final version
1.3	24.02.2026	Reviewed version after Periodic Review Evaluation